

Kelp Restoration Assessment Report for *California*

: Modeling the Future of Kelp Forests Under Climate Change in California

Authors:

Samantha Aguilar⁴, Zahra Amir², Joy Herzberger³,
Karli Klein⁵, Jerelyn Lee, Chotcheyrith Leng¹, Arianna
Martinez, Naomie Martinez, Charlie Mitchell², Maps
Rasmussen⁵, Ethan Tigerino², Chris Timlin-Broussard⁸,
Herbert Virula⁶, Zee Zetino

What is influencing where
GIANT KELP and **BULL KELP**
can grow in California now and in the
future?

What are the challenges and
opportunities for kelp restoration in
California?

Here we consider ecological, economic,
and sociopolitical factors to address
these questions.

Contributors

Lead Authors:	Samantha Aguilar ⁴ , Zahra Amir ² , Joy Herzberger ³ , Karli Klein ⁵ , Jerelyn Lee, Chotcheyrith Ieng ¹ , Arianna Martinez, Naomie Martinez, Charlie Mitchell ² , Maps Rasmussen ⁵ , Ethan Tigerino ² , Chris Timlin-Broussard ⁸ , Herbert Virula ⁶ , Zee Zetino
Affiliations:	(1) East Los Angeles College, (2) El Camino College, (3) Los Angeles City College, (4) Pasadena City College, (5) Pierce College, (6) Santa Monica City College, (7) West Los Angeles College, (8) Los Angeles Valley College.
Editor:	Ariel Levi Simons, PhD
Project Coordinator:	Ariel Levi Simons, PhD
Advisors:	Emma Akmakdijan (Pepperdine University), Victor P. Corona, PhD (West Los Angeles College), Michael J Farrell (Los Angeles City College), Crystal A. Ng, PhD (Pierce College), Laura Rink (Associate Director of Operations for the Heal the Bay Aquarium)
Director for the CA Center for Climate Change Education:	Joana (Jo) Tavares-Reager, PhD
Designed by:	Maps Rasmussen
Reviewers:	Robert Ellis (Orange Coast College), Crystal A. Ng, PhD (Pierce College), Laura Rink (Associate Director of Operations for the Heal the Bay Aquarium)
Photography / Artwork by:	Taylor Griffith, Alec Battistoni, Samantha Aguilar, Karli Klein, Maps Rasmussen, Zee Zetino

This report was produced by the California Center for Climate Change Education at West Los Angeles College, in partnership with KelpArk and AltaSea, and with support from the U.S. Department of Labor (DOL) Community Projects Program, the State of California Appropriations funding (AB 1913), and the Blue Economy and Climate Action Pathways (BECAP) initiative, a Strong Workforce Regional Program facilitated by the Los Angeles Regional Consortium (LARC).

You can learn more at the [Kelp Project's Website](#)

LAND AND WATER AWARENESS

We acknowledge that California is the home of many Native Tribal communities. We respectfully recognize that the land and waters we reside on are the home of Native peoples -- the original stewards and protectors. Today, what is known as the greater Los Angeles area, is the unceded home to both federally recognized and unrecognized tribes who seek land and water sovereignty, along with truth and reconciliation. There are currently 109 federally recognized Native tribes in California and many non-federally recognized tribes, including a State list of 62 non-federally recognized tribes for cultural and sacred site protection. We recognize the unceded lands of the CHUMASH, TONGVA, GABRIELENO, TATAVIAM, and the KIZH TRIBAL communities who are the descendants and bearers of foundational systems of memory, prayer, sacred ceremony, and of both multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary sciences. From the white sage protection to kelp forest restoration, may the wind and breath be the original peoples fervent messages to

reconnecting back to the ancestral ways of being and coexisting.

Through our continuous efforts, may we move forward towards the past, present, and future, understanding the need to center Native people— cultural, social, and ecological knowledge and practices when discussing and acting on kelp restoration.

If you would like to learn about whose lands you reside on, visit native-land.ca.

Words by Zee Zetino

Special Thanks to the following organizations, professionals, and community leaders who offered their knowledge and support to make this possible:

OCEAN RAINFOREST

CULTURED ABALONE FARM

LAURA RINK, Associate Director of Operations, Heal the Bay Aquarium

NATHAN CHURCHES, Co-founder & Chief Science Officer, Koldfast Aquaculture

AMANDA VANDIGGELEN, Senior Environmental Scientist, California Department of Fish and Wildlife

KAREN MARTIN, Professor of Biology, Pepperdine Seaver College

ELIJAH MASERU, PhD. student, UCLA in the Institute of Environment and Sustainability

KYLE CAVANAUGH, Vice Director, Marine Center; Professor of Geography, UCLA

ROD FUJITA, Marine biologist, Ocean Innovations

CHANCE ENGLISH, Postdoctoral scholar in Microbial oceanography, UCSB's Interdepartmental Graduate Program in Marine Science

MATT EDWARDS, Professor of Biology, SDSU

DAVID GILLETT, Ecologist, The Southern California Coastal Water Research Project (SCCWRP)

GRETCHEN GREBE, Ph.D. Environmental Scientist, Aquaculture and Aquatic Resources, University of Maine

SEAN ANDERSON, Professor and Chair of the Environmental Science and Resource Management Program (ESRM), California State University Channel Islands

JARRETT VAN DEN BERGH, Senior Software Engineer

SIMONA AUGYTE, Aquaculture Specialist, California SeaGrant

HALLIE BROWN, Coastal Stories Project Associate, The California Marine Sanctuary Foundation (CMSF)

STEPHANIE MITCHELL, Senior Consultant on the California State Assembly Water, Parks and Wildlife Committee

RAFAEL CUEVAS URIBE, Professor, CalPoly Humboldt

LUCIE GAW, Graduate Student, Moss Landing Marine Laboratories/San Jose State University

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Securing a future for California's kelp forests requires a dual strategy:

focusing conservation and restoration efforts in climate refugia areas while reforming state policies that impede vital restoration work.

Objective:

The overall goal of this project was to study the various issues connected to the restoration of kelp forests in California, with a focus on *giant kelp* and *bull kelp*, the two dominant canopy-forming kelp in the state.

Abstract

Giant kelp (*Macrocystis pyrifera*) and Bull kelp (*Nereocystis luetkeana*) are foundational species in California's coastal ecosystems. These essential ecosystems are caught between the pressures of rising ocean temperatures and destructive grazing by booming sea urchin populations. This project maps the potential future for these kelp forests by modeling how their suitable habitats will shift by the year 2100 under various climate change scenarios. Our results forecast a coast with less kelp overall and a distinct northward shift in habitat for both species. The projections are especially concerning for bull kelp, which is expected to vanish from southern and central California. However, the models also identify critical climate refugia where giant kelp may persist, particularly in Monterey Bay and around the Channel Islands.

Beyond these ecological projections, our work confronts the human barriers to conservation. We found that California's complex and slow permitting process often hinders restoration projects, standing in contrast to more streamlined approaches in other states. This report integrates the scientific models with an analysis of these policy roadblocks, the economic role of kelp in the Blue Economy, and the vital importance of public communication. Ultimately, we conclude that securing a future for California's kelp forests requires a dual strategy: focusing conservation and restoration efforts on the identified climate refugia while reforming the state policies that currently impede that vital work.

PHOTO: TAYLOR GRIFFITH

BULL & GIANT KELP

NAMES HAVE THE POWER TO SHAPE THOUGHT AND FOCUS.

The two main species we've studied for this report, *bull kelp* and *giant kelp*, are known by a variety of names, each reflecting the focus of the cultures that named them.

Bull kelp, named so in English because its whip-like shape resembles a bullwhip, is known scientifically by the name *N. luetkeana*. This name partially reflects the Greek term for 'mermaid's bladder', *Nereocystis*, as each bull kelp stalk ends in a large bulb-like structure.

At the northern end of California, the Tolowa Dee-ni' call it Ghvltlh-k'vsh. Farther south, the Kashia Band of the Pomo know it as *chanamá*. In Kodiak, Alaska, it's called *nasquluq* in Alutiiq. Near Coos Bay, Oregon, Hanis speakers call it *qálaqas*. Even 19th-century Russian sailors had a name for it—they called it "sea otter cabbage."

In English, and in Greek-derived scientific terminology, giant kelp has a name reflecting its large size and numerous bulbous floats. The scientific term for it, *M. pyrifera*, stems from the roots 'macro' (large) and 'kystis' (bladder), and 'pyrifera' from Latin means "pear-bearing," a reference to the shape of its bladders.

In Chile, *M. pyrifera* is known as *huiró*, *sargazo gigante*, and *cachiyuyo*. In Australia and South Africa, it is generally referred to as giant kelp or giant bladder kelp.

In Tlingit, giant kelp is called *daaw*, which means "broad kelp that herring spawns on." In the Haida language found in British Columbia, it is known as *sk'at'uuga*, which translates to "popping by stepping on." In Nuuchah-nulth, giant kelp is called *ʔiʔinmak'uk*, meaning "nipple-like." In Makah, it is known as *ch'ach'aʔaqtł*, which translates to "water-inside."

PHOTO : ALEC BATTISTONI

Table of contents.

1.0	Summary	17
2.0	Biology	21
3.0	Modeling	30
4.0	Policy	52
5.0	Science Communication	62
6.0	Blue Economy & Workforce	88
7.0	Pre-Glossary	100
8.0	Glossary	103
9.0	Citations	112

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Goals

1

Biology & Restoration

How does the physical environment affect their metabolism, growth, and reproductive cycles? How do these species of kelp interact with other species along coastal California? In this section we will synthesize our most current understanding of the biological functioning of these kelp species to help address these questions.

2

Ecological Modeling

In modeling we seek to predict the current suitable habitats for giant kelp and bull kelp, and to identify the key environmental variables driving their distribution. Following this goal we also sought to model suitable kelp habitats under three climate scenarios, as well as identify potential climate refugia locations for both kelp species by the end of the 21st century.

3

Policy and Governance

With regards to environmental policy our goals are as follows: (1) To map out the current regulatory environment governing kelp forest restoration and farming, (2) Determine the best paths for funding restoration efforts, (3) Determine best practices for managing both kelp forest restoration and farming from other parts of the United States such as Hawaii and Maine.

4

Science Communication

With science communications we seek to build a better understanding of how to use arts and storytelling towards the ecological restoration of kelp forests. This involves the use of media to help engage the general public towards restoration efforts, but it also goes deeper towards the deep history of kelp forests in the ecosystem and human communities' relationships with them. These discussions go into the role of language in shaping thought around how we interact with our environment, and on the nature of what the term restoration even means in dynamic coastal ecosystems.

5

Workforce and Blue Economy

The goal of our project is to identify the economic value of kelp forests, to advocate for sustainable practices for a growing blue economy, and to highlight leaders in this sector. Following these goals we examined the economic impacts of giant kelp (*M. pyrifera*), bull kelp (*N. luetkeana*), and the ecosystems they live in through the following lens: conservation, restoration, aquaculture, and social sustainability.

Guiding Questions

1

BIOLOGY

How do we utilize kelp biology to best inform restoration practices?

2

ECOLOGICAL MODELING

Where could kelp grow in California by 2100?

3

POLICY & GOVERNANCE

How will policy uplift restoration efforts?

4

SCIENCE COMMUNICATIONS

How do we get people to care and to act with regards to kelp forests?

5

WORKFORCE AND BLUE ECONOMY

In a growing Californian Blue Economy how does kelp fit in?

Summary

1.1 Biology & Restoration

This section is intended to provide biological context for restoration practices. By reviewing literature, critical factors that had the potential to influence or impact current and future restoration practices were determined. The restoration methods practiced in California were analyzed to determine their efficiency, with recommendations on the need for any future developments. Furthermore, the future benefits of kelp restoration were addressed to inform the public that there is still a need for additional research.

PHOTO : TAYLOR GRIFFITH

1.2 Ecological Modeling

To develop our habitat suitability models, we obtained kelp occurrence records from 2010-2020 via the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), and corresponding marine environmental data from Bio-Oracle. Various models were then run, using a random forest algorithm, predicting suitable habitats for giant kelp and bull kelp under current and predicted climatic conditions. Future climatic conditions were based on three distinct climate change scenarios (Shared Socio-economic Pathways, SSPs) to predict shifts in suitable habitat over time. We also used these models of predicted suitable habitat to identify potential climate refugia, which are areas predicted to remain as potential suitable habitat across all future projections.

Based on the current environmental models from 2010-2020, giant kelp habitat is currently concentrated in central and southern California, while bull kelp thrives along the northern California coast. Future climate scenarios predict a northwards shift for both species. While bull kelp is projected to be present along the northern Californian coast, the species is projected to recede from waters south of the southern California bight. In contrast, while giant kelp habitat is also projected to shrink in area, key locations are expected to persist as climate refugia in areas like Monterey Bay, Big Sur, and around the Channel Islands.

Overall, the findings point to a future with a diminished geographic footprint for both keystone kelp species, with the decline predicted to be more rapid and severe for bull kelp.

PHOTO : TAYLOR GRIFFITH

Summary

1.3 Policy & Governance

The policy team looked into how legislation influences the success or failure of kelp forest restoration projects. Our goal was to understand how regulatory structures, funding opportunities, and agency collaboration affect the pace and scale of restoration. By examining California's permitting requirements and comparing them to Maine and Hawaii, we aimed to find barriers that slow progress and highlight strategies from other states that can be applied to California's framework. Our findings highlight that the future of kelp restoration in California depends on policies that not only protect ecosystems but also enable innovation and long term resilience.

1.4 Science Communications

Community engagement and art are vital tools for better enabling equitable restoration efforts. With art and science communication we explore alternative mediums to hold conversations around the warming and changing California coastlines, striving to bridge the gap between scientific jargon and public knowledge in an equitable way. Challenging outreach efforts, exploring the powerful use of AI to best aid our future, and questioning the ethics of human involvement. We also aim to include indigenous knowledge and local stakeholders, offering a renewed sense of hope in a space where climate conversations can feel heavy.

Our findings highlight that the future of kelp restoration in California depends on policies that not only protect ecosystems but also enable innovation and long term resilience.

Summary

1.5 Blue Economy

The blue economy focuses on the development of technologies and practices focused on sustainable use of marine resources. We aim to explore the economic feasibility of kelp restoration projects along the coastline of California; and we focus on the relationship between Californian kelp forests and the blue economy through the following lenses: conservation, restoration & monitoring, aquaculture, and social sustainability.

Our findings show the following: conservation, restoration, and monitoring of kelp forests have economic benefits, especially to coastal communities, social collaboration in restoration projects as well as aquaculture aid in the overall success of a project, and workforce development is an underutilized asset in California. Overall, we conclude that sustainable use of the California coastline must include social collaboration with local communities, including tribal and indigenous groups, more streamlined policy, and the continued funding of blue economy sector training and education programs.

PHOTO : TAYLOR GRIFFITH

Biology

Authors : Samantha Aguilar, Ethan Tigerino, Herbert Virula

2.1 Introduction

Geographic range and reproduction of giant kelp and bull kelp

Giant kelp and **bull kelp**, are species of brown macroalgae belonging to the order Laminariales which are native to the coast of California (Springer et al., 2007, Graham et al., 2007). In North America, giant kelp is distributed from Alaska down to Mexico. Within this range, giant kelp can be found in intertidal environments at depths up to approximately 60 meters (Graham et al., 2007). Bull kelp forms kelp beds from Unmak Island, AK down to Point Conception, CA (Springer et al., 2007). Similar to giant kelp, bull kelp beds are found in shallow rocky marine habitats (Springer et al., 2007). Both species act as fundamental members of their ecosystems by fueling food webs and forming habitats for other organisms (Springer et al., 2007, Graham et al., 2007). Their structures promote biodiversity and support nurseries through the habitat provided by their structures (Graham et al., 2007, Springer et al., 2007). An important distinction between the two species is that bull kelp is an annual, while giant kelp is a perennial; this difference in life history has major implications for restoration and survival, as bull kelp relies entirely on successful yearly recruitment, whereas giant kelp can recover through the persistence of adult macroalgae.

Giant kelp and bull kelp, like all kelp, exhibit two morphologies in their life cycle: the microscopic gametophyte stage and macroscopic sporophyte stage (Graham et al., 2007). Adult sporophytes will release spores that become either female or

male gametophytes (Graham et al., 2007). Sperm from male gametophytes will fertilize eggs released from female gametophytes, creating embryonic sporophytes that will grow into juvenile kelp recruits (Graham et al., 2007). These recruits will ultimately become adult sporophytes (Graham et al., 2007).

NUTRIENTS

In general, kelp requires nitrogen, phosphates, sunlight, and other minerals and vitamins for growth (Navarrete et al., 2021, Weigel et al., 2023). Nitrogen, in particular, both enables growth and may help thermal stress response for adult kelps (Weigel et al., 2023). Among the more important minerals needed for growth, iron can also act as a limiting nutrient beyond coastal waters (Paine et al., 2023). There is less known about the nutritional needs for juvenile kelp in their microscopic stage (Weigel et al., 2023). Additionally, the precise nutrients needed on a species or population level for kelps are still being determined via research (Hollarsmith et al., 2022).

2.2 Abiotic Factors

THERMAL TOLERANCE

Giant kelp and bull kelp generally have similar thermal tolerances. Giant kelp can produce juvenile sporophytes between 11 and 20°C (Deysher & Dean, 1986). Bull kelp gametophytes prefer a temperature range of 10 to 16°C, while sporophytes prefer one of 16 to 18°C (Weigel et al., 2023). While giant kelp can adapt to different ranges in temperature to some degree (Hollarsmith et al., 2020), such local adaptation has not been shown in bull kelp (Weigel et al., 2023).

How do we
utilize kelp
biology to
best inform
restoration
practices?

When considering kelp restoration and transplantation, it is important to determine a specific site's population thermal tolerance (Hollarsmith et al., 2020). In some instances, kelp in higher temperature areas can be outcompeted by other macroalgae that can tolerate high temperatures as well, such as the invasive *Sargassum horneri* (Bishop, 2021).

Since these studies are primarily conducted in laboratory settings, it should be determined whether these findings can be translated well to the field.

CO₂ AND OCEAN ACIDIFICATION

Various kelp species, such as giant kelp and bull kelp, may benefit from the increase in CO₂ associated with climate change (HongYan et al., 2008). Despite this, research has shown that their growth rate may be enhanced, but the rate of photosynthesis does not show such an increase (HongYan et al., 2008, Kroeker et al., 2013). Acidification, enhanced by increases in CO₂, can also lead to higher organic carbon accumulation in sediment (Ravaglioli et al., 2019). A major threat is the rise of "weedy" turf algae

that outcompete kelp recruits under acidification and warming temperatures (Connell & Russell, 2010). More studies should be done in the field to understand impacts of turf algae on giant kelp and bull kelp in California.

2.3 Biotic Factors

GRAZERS

There are several species that graze giant kelp and bull kelp, of which the purple sea urchin is one of the more influential with regard to influencing forest cover (Pearse, 2006). Purple sea urchin populations have experienced explosive growth due to a loss of their predators, which turn kelp forests into urchin barrens that can stretch thousands of kilometers along coastlines (Filbee-Dexter & Scheibling, 2014). The rapid expansion of purple sea urchin populations in recent years can largely be attributed to the loss of predatory species, such as the overharvested seven native species of California abalone (Wing et al., 2015). For kelp restoration projects, an important consideration has become how to properly manage sea urchin populations (Miller & Shears, 2022).

Kelp needs nitrogen, phosphates, sunlight, and other minerals and vitamins to grow (Navarrete et al., 2021, Weigel et al., 2023)

PHOTO : TAYLOR GRIFFITH

PREDATOR-PREY INTERACTIONS

Predator-prey interactions are important for maintaining kelp forest stability. In the case of urchins, there must be at least one predatory species keeping their populations in check (Eisaguirre et al. 2020). One of the urchin's greatest predators, the sunflower star, has been listed as critically endangered due to sea star wasting syndrome (Eisaguirre et al. 2020). The loss of this predator along the west coast of North America has led to coastal environments with lower biodiversity, largely through the fragmentation of once-complex food webs (Schultz et al. 2016). Reintroducing the sunflower sea star is a commonly discussed topic, but there is uncertainty as to whether their reintroduction would be effective in helping to moderate purple sea urchin populations and maintain food web complexity (Eisaguirre et al., 2020). Nevertheless, active efforts are underway in Northern California to rear and release sunflower sea stars, alongside ongoing research evaluating their survival, ecological impacts, and potential role in kelp forest recovery; similar aquaculture and recovery efforts are also being conducted in Southern California by organizations such as Heal the Bay.

Other urchin predators include sea otters, the California sheephead, and the spiny lobster. Sea otters are particularly effective at managing

sea urchins in central and northern California, but their populations are still recovering from overhunting that occurred from 1711-1911 in along the western coast of North America which wiped out over 99% of their Californian population (Anderson et al., 1996; Scarborough et al., 2022). Sheephead and spiny lobster have been overfished in many areas, including Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) that allow for their collection (Yates et al., 2022). However, policy changes, such as creating MPAs that forbid collection, can successfully increase the populations of these two predators (Eisaguirre et al., 2020). Predators have been observed preferring sea urchins in kelp forests rather than urchins in barrens that have very little gonad biomass (Eisaguirre et al., 2020), which bodes well for long-term efforts at kelp forest restoration.

MICROBIOME

Kelp microbiomes, that is the community of microorganisms living on and in kelp tissues, are species-specific and are generally dominated by bacteria. Bacterial communities can differ depending on region, season, developmental stage, and even individual organisms (Weigel & Pfister, 2019).

Microbiomes have been shown to provide the nutrients necessary for kelp growth and development (Aguirre & Shwartzman, 2024, Weigel et al., 2022), as well as aid in kelp degradation (Chance et al., 2025), which allows carbon to sink into sediments.

However, there is still incredibly limited research on the kelp microbiomes in general, as well as issues with reproducibility for some findings (Emily Aguirre, Kelp Ark, pers. comm.). While we may not have extensive insight yet, one avenue of research relevant to kelp restoration is crafting probiotic and prebiotic cocktails that can help outplanted kelp growth and survivability (Li et al., 2023, Osborne et al., 2024).

2.4 The importance of restoration and current restoration practices in California

Kelp forest restoration offers significant ecological and economic benefits, primarily through enhancing biodiversity in restored areas. Giant kelp and bull kelp forests attract a wide array of marine species, many of which are economically valuable and contribute to the sustainability of fisheries (Eger et al., 2022a, Graham et al., 2007, Springer et al., 2007). Beyond biodiversity, kelp can also help with bioremediation of marine pollutants. For example, giant kelp is metal-tolerant and can absorb pollutants such as copper (Evans & Edwards, 2011).

Since 1958 there have been a total of 83 kelp forest restoration projects in California, 12 of which are currently active (Farrer, 2025). Restoration projects employ a variety of strategies such as artificial reef construction, community-based monitoring, grazer control, seeding, transplantation, and drift kelp deployment (Farrer, 2025).

Grazer control is primarily focused on urchins. The most efficient and effective method of doing this is by culling urchins (Miller & Shears, 2022, Miller et al., 2022). Quicklime can be particularly effective in killing urchins, however quicklime harms other organisms on the reef (Brooks et al., 2020) and as a result this method has been retired in California (Wilson & McPeak, 1982; Brooks et al. 2020). The next best option for urchin culling has been found to be crushing. This technique is carried out by scuba divers, and it can clear out 1,400 urchins at low densities ($2.0/m^2$), and up to 3,000 urchins per hour at densities of ($30/m^2$) (Wilson & McPeak, 1982, Bacon, 2024). However, studies suggest crushing can harm reefs (Wilson & McPeak, 1982; Bacon, 2024) and may not be a viable long-term solution (Miller et al., 2022), so these should be considered when designing kelp restoration projects. Other methods like hand harvesting can be successful, which the California non-profit Reef Check has been doing (Lepczyk et al., 2020).

Restoration efforts can still fail due to factors like incompatible substrate, selecting too small a restoration area, and climate change (Danner et al., 1994, Earp et al., 2022, Ambrose & Swarbrick, 1989, Turner et al., 1969).

Site selection is a critical component to kelp restoration. Before restoration projects can begin, they must identify the cause of kelp forest decline, the rate of decline, and the most appropriate restoration method that would not harm the local ecosystem (Eger et al., 2022b). Recently, a framework was developed using spatial data to show the priority levels for potential restoration sites for bull kelp and giant kelp in California (Giraldo-Ospina et al., 2025). There are other ongoing projects focused on building site selection frameworks that incorporate marine policy, such as the Morpho Project at the National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis (NCEAS). Recurring limitations for site selection include the cost of maintaining the restoration area, the need for incorporation of local communities, and environmental stressors (Eger et al., 2022b, Elias et al., 2021). There is a general lack of understanding of the potential for kelp to adapt due to climate change (Vranken et al., 2021). Overall, there is still much to learn about how climate change may influence site selection in the future.

Kelp restoration offers significant ecological and economic benefits, primarily by enhancing biodiversity.

PHOTO : TAYLOR GRIFFITH

2.5 Challenges to restoration and future benefits

Challenges to kelp restoration include permitting delays (McHugh et al., 2025), climate change, and the need to often integrate multiple methods. Climate stressors, particularly marine heat waves, are leading to a global decline of kelp forests (Arafteh-Dalmau et al., 2020). One potential avenue to address this is developing breeding methods for thermally tolerant individuals and creating seed banks (Eger et al., 2022a). Restoration also calls for the use of multiple methods, since manually culling urchins may not be entirely effective given that urchin barrens can be large, stable, and self-reinforcing (Filbee-Dexter & Sheibling, 2014, Miller et al., 2022). The use of autonomous robots to replace scuba divers has been proposed as a potential solution (Eger et al., 2022a), as well as using multiple restoration methods at the same time, for example grazer control paired with transplantation and seeding (Farrer, 2025). Ultimately, targeting the larger scale causes of kelp forest decline, such as overfishing, pollution, and greenhouse gas emissions, is also necessary for successful kelp restoration (Eger et al., 2022a).

In terms of benefits, restoring kelp forests can contribute to global carbon sequestration. Since kelp absorbs CO_2 , they can offset excess CO_2 from the burning of fossil fuels (Doney et al., 2025). When macroalgae detach, drift, and sink, the carbon is sequestered into the sediment (Krause-Jensen & Duarte 2016). Annually, kelp forests around the world are estimated to sequester 4.91 teragrams of carbon (Eger et al., 2023). However, it is unknown how much carbon is sequestered by California kelp forests alone. To better contextualize the benefits of kelp restoration, we need to quantify current annual carbon sequestration in this region.

Giant kelp and bull kelp can also be used for bioremediation. Both species can absorb nitrogen and phosphorus from agriculture and residential areas (Matt Edwards, pers. comm.). Giant kelp can bioaccumulate heavy metals like zinc

and copper (Evans & Edwards, 2011). However, there are interactions with metal absorption as increasing zinc does not affect copper uptake, but increasing copper may impact zinc intake (Evans & Edwards, 2011). Overall, more research is needed on the limits of heavy metal and pollutant absorption. One study showed that even a short, seven day pulse of metals (copper and cadmium) and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), led to mortality in juvenile giant kelp (Jara-Yáñez et al., 2021). Though research is still limited, the potential for giant kelp and bull kelp to improve water quality and ecosystem health should not be overlooked as a benefit to kelp restoration.

Though research is still limited, the **potential** for giant kelp and bull kelp to **improve water quality and ecosystem health** should not be overlooked as a benefit to kelp restoration.

Both species act as fundamental members of their ecosystems by fueling food webs and forming habitats for other organisms (Springer et al., 2007, Graham et al., 2007)

PHOTO : TAYLOR GRIFFITH

Modeling

Authors : Jerelyn Lee, Chris Timlin-Broussard

3.1 Introduction

Understanding the role of human impacts upon ecosystems is becoming increasingly important over the coming century (Lewis & Maslin, 2015)

A large portion of coastal California's ecosystems are supported by the canopy-forming brown kelp of California, giant kelp and bull kelp (Fragkopoulou et al., 2022). Giant kelp and bull kelp are the dominant canopy-forming kelp species in California, though their distribution is not uniform (Carr & Reed, 2016).

Species Distribution Models (SDMs) aid in the identification of sites where kelp is likely to persist, an important factor in aquaculture and restoration planning (Assis et al., 2024). While there are a wide variety of SDMs, they are all based on the idea of predicting the likeliest distribution of a species given data on what the environment is like where individuals have been observed and what the environmental conditions are across the rest of a study area.

SDMs have been developed over the last 25 years, yet still frequently suffer from methodological flaws such as low sample counts, limited representation of a species' habitats, inappropriate selection of environmental factors, and how differing current and future conditions undermine the reliability of these models (Araújo et al., 2019; Santini et al., 2021). With these caveats in mind, SDMs can still provide some insight into potentially long-term viable sites for our target species of brown kelp.

This distribution varies both spatially and temporally, and has consisted of periods of excep-

tionally low coverage in 1897-1899 as well as 2014-2016 (Selgrath et al., 2024). Outside of these notable events, multidecadal trends of kelp biomass density have been associated with low-frequency oscillations in sea surface temperature (Bell et al., 2018).

SDMs have also been used to predict that giant kelp may see the limit of its southern range on the north Pacific coastline shift northward to the Santa Barbara Channel (Gonzalez-Aragon et al., 2024). To our knowledge, few SDMs were found that focused on our species of interest in California waters, in part due to the relatively novel approach that these models represent in the marine environment (Rodrigues et al., 2022). We expected our results to show a similar poleward shift as previous work has found when globally modelling kelp forests (Assis et al., 2024).

Kelp coverage in MPAs has declined, and is expected to recede further under climate shifts predicted under Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) 4.5 & 8.5, which represents levels of global warming of 2.7 and 4.4 degrees C respectively by the end of the century (Figure B). Under these warming scenarios the expected range of our two kelp species of interest is expected to shift, but by varying degrees between them (Young et al., 2025; Assis et al., 2024). SDMs have projected the overall global area of kelp forests to decline by 15% by the year 2100 under the SSP 8.5 pathway. (Assis et al., 2024).

Taking these shifts into account can help select more long-term resilient MPA locations (Young et al., 2025). Analyzing recent environmental conditions has led other researchers to highlight 44% of kelp forest sites in Californian MPAs as mid-to-high-priority for restoration (Giraldo-Ospina et al., 2025).

**Our work
predicts
kelp will be
present in
California
in 2100**

With only 20.9% of giant kelp under MPA protection in central California, declining to less than 1% in Baja California, Mexico, many existing kelp populations may be vulnerable to oncoming climate shocks (Arafeh-Dalmau et al., 2021).

We endeavor to build on previous work identifying likely kelp refugia locations in order to aid the selection of restoration sites within Californian MPAs (Young et al., 2025). Such identification will be critical if California intends to meet its 30x30 aspirations in the most effective manner (Eger et al., 2025).

Depending on marine climatic conditions, the line between aquaculture and restoration has become increasingly blurred (Costa-Pierce, 2002; Patterson, 2019; Overton et al., 2023). Kelp can potentially provide for biofuel production, water quality regulation through nutrient removal, carbon sequestration, and providing habitat for other marine species (Sharmila et al., 2021; Jiang et al., 2020; Eger et al., 2023). Ecosystem benefits can be extended from appropriately designed aquaculture systems (Overton et al., 2023). For instance, there is a positive correlation be-

tween kelp cultivation and bivalve calcification, a boon to these species of commercial interest (Li et al., 2021; Azra et al., 2021). Thus, understanding the potential distribution of kelp species, whether natural or cultivated, is vital for future coastal management and development (Gorman et al., 2013). However, our research showed limited implementation of SDMs so far in aquaculture planning.

Previous studies have attempted to model the maximal available ecological feasible area for algae cultivation, 20.8 million km² within Economic Exclusivity Zones globally (Liu et al., 2023). The majority of which consists of temperate coastal waters such as the California coastline (Liu et al., 2023; Payne et al., 2012).

SDMs could also be employed to reduce policy overburden by selecting sites relatively absent of endangered species, as well as aiding in aquaculture site selection (Farmer et al., 2022; Falconer et al., 2016). We aim to extend this approach, by identifying sites that are predicted to be suitable habitats for kelp across three climatic scenarios.

As our economies continue to exacerbate climate change, the search for climate solutions has extended into the marine environment under the guise of 'blue carbon' (Lewis & Maslin, 2015; Macreadie et al., 2021; Gao et al., 2022).

PHOTO : TAYLOR GRIFFITH

Kelp offers significant potential for carbon sequestration with Net Primary Production (NPP), that is the rate at which biomass is generated via photosynthesis, of macroalgae (Pessarrodona et al., 2023; Duarte et al., 2022; Krause-Jenson et al., 2018). With first-order estimates ranging from 11% of NPP being potentially sequestered, though much depends on local conditions (Krause-Jenson & Duarte, 2016; Pessarrodona et al., 2023).

Such assessments have been published for a variety of habitats including seagrasses and salt marshes in California, as well as farmed *Saccharina latissima* in Strangford Lough, Northern Ireland, and for three macroalgae species in the Falkland Isles (Ward et al., 2021; Dolliver & O'Connor, 2021; Bayley et al., 2021). As SDMs focus more on habitat than biomass, and given the absence of NPP estimates for the entirety of California, we see a potential for future work to give a first-order estimation of carbon sequestration for both giant kelp and bull kelp across the California coast (Rassweiler et al., 2008).

SDMs are widely utilized as surrogates to describe the complex confluence of environmental factors that contribute to defining a species' habitat (Robinson et al., 2017). In marine environments, these habitats are shifting both rapidly and non-linearly in response to changing climatic conditions (Burrows et al., 2011).

SDMs can be utilized to predict the future distribution of kelp, but they necessitate an analysis of the spatial and temporal drivers that impact habitat suitability (Giraldo-Ospina et al., 2025). These include abiotic factors such as nutrient availability and temperature, which have been associated with long-term kelp ecosystem viability, as well as biotic factors such as over-grazing from herbivores (Giraldo-Ospina et al., 2025).

Whether gradual or episodic, temperature rises are globally associated with kelp decline, and confluences of abiotic and biotic factors have tipped bull kelp forest ecosystems in northern California into severe canopy loss as well as collapsing into 'Urchin Barrens' (Duarte et al., 2022; Rogers-Bennett & Catton, 2019).

These heat-related events have been noted to induce a recovery lag that persists for multiple years (Selgrath et al., 2024). However, post

heat-disturbance pathways for giant kelp on small spatial scales in the Santa Barbara Channel were neither uniform nor linear (Urigoiti Crespo, 2024). Given the coarse spatial resolution of future marine environmental data, our models could not possibly detect a delineation.

Better integration of biotic, spatial, and temporal factors result in a more refined model of suitable kelp habitat (Klaassen et al., 2025).

For example, it is anticipated that marine heatwaves could be predicted up to 12 months in advance, a timescale far shorter than the temporal scope of our research (Jacox et al., 2022). Additionally, the utilization of density data for purple sea urchins has been used to model kelp forest density through grazing (Giraldo-Ospina et al., 2025).

However, density information is not ascertainable from occurrence data alone. Thus, due to the limits of data, complexity, and computation, our approach focuses on average abiotic conditions associated with three climate scenarios, as well as the underlying bathymetric conditions associated with kelp habitats.

3.2 Methods

Species occurrence records were downloaded from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) for both kelp species (GBIF.org, 2025). We are using the bounding area between 46.25N and 22.89N latitude, and then -124.5W and -114.1W longitude, as this corresponds to our study area between the southern boundary of Baja California and the northern boundary of Oregon. To ensure data quality and relevance, the records were subjected to several filtering steps.

First, a temporal filter was applied to retain only records from 2010 to the 2020, aligning with the temporal resolution of the environmental data. This filtering yielded 538 occurrences for giant kelp and 97 occurrences for bull kelp. To mitigate spatial sampling bias, we thinned the records to a minimum distance of 9.26 km, matching the spatial resolution of our environmental data (Gonzalez-Aragon et al., 2024).

We generated three times the random background points across the study area to characterize the available environmental conditions of our study area and ensure sufficient background points for the marine environment (Gonzalez-Aragon et al., 2024). These background points are needed to sample environmental conditions at locations without any kelp data, which is used in our SDMs to help predict conditions where kelp is unlikely to grow.

To model the species' current distribution, we used marine environmental variables averaged from data collected from the period 2010 to 2020. These data were sourced from Bio-Oracle v3.0 (Assis et al., 2024). This environmental data, representing factors such as sea surface temperature and the concentration of nitrates, has a spatial resolution of 5 arc-min latitude-longitude corresponding to a square approximately 9.26 km on a side.

This report utilizes five specific environmental predictors, chosen for their impact on kelp survival, growth, and reproduction. Sea Surface Temperature (Mean and Maximum) is the primary factor, as kelp distribution is highly sensitive to thermal thresholds; exceeding these limits causes rapid mortality due to physiological stress and nutrient limitations. Nitrate Concentration is included because it is the main limiting macro-nutrient for macroalgal growth in this area and is often inversely related to temperature.

Current Velocity accounts for water movement, which is critical for nutrient transport across the algal boundary layer, although excessive speed can result in mechanical detachment. Salinity and pH characterize the fundamental marine chemical niche and address potential stressors linked to freshwater runoff or ocean acidification. Cloud cover was incorporated to represent the light energy available for photosynthesis, which strictly delimits the maximum depth range of kelp forests.

Our models of the current spatial distribution of kelp species were built using these environmental data, and kelp occurrence locations. To predict future distributions of kelp we then reran our SDMs, but incorporated predicted future marine conditions as modeled by the Bio-Oracle team. These folding environmental data were

used to modeled on a decade by decade basis out to 2100 ([LINK TO TABLE](#)).

Occurrence and background points, as well as our environmental layers (current and future), were used to create a series of SDMS in order to predict the spatial distributions of suitable kelp habitats (Tyberghein et al., 2012).

For current climatic conditions each kelp SDM was constructed as follows: (1) 80% of presence and background points were randomly selected, (2) Environmental values at those locations were extracted using the function `extract` from the R package `raster` (Hijmans et al., 2015), (3) These extracted values were then used to predict kelp presence/absence by running a random forest model using the function `tuneRF` in the R package `randomForest` (Liaw & Wiener, 2002).

To run an individual SDM we used a random forest algorithm, run using the R language. We used R as it is open source, freely available, and commonly used in the biological sciences. A random forest algorithm was used as it is both accurate, and relatively straightforward in its process. It works by constructing decision trees which fork at each variable in the model, with the tips of the branches containing results from the input data corresponding to the presence or absence of the species being modeled. These trees are constructed using a fraction of the total data, with an averaged decision tree constructed representing the likeliest pathway through all of the environmental variables to an output state representing the presence or absence of a species.

Each model was then run 100 times, with a new set of randomly selected data, and the results aggregated. Each model output consisted of the following outputs: (1) A map predicting suitable habitat for a selected kelp species, (2) The relative importance of the model variables as extracted using the `randomForest` function `importance`, (3) A measure of model accuracy.

Model accuracy was evaluated by testing how well it predicted the presence or absence of kelp in the remaining 20% of data used as a testing set.

The metric we used to assess the accuracy of our models is given by the true skill statistic (TSS). This metric is calculated using the true positive rate (sensitivity), how often a kelp is correctly predicted to be somewhere, the true negative rate (specificity), how often a kelp is correctly predicted to be absent. The formula for the TSS is given as $TSS = \text{sensitivity} + \text{specificity} - 1$ (Gonzalez-Aragon et al., 2024). The range of TSS values runs from -1 to 1, with 1 representing the highest level of model accuracy. Habitat suitability was then visualized by summing the 100 prediction maps, and variable importance by their average importance values as calculated using their mean decrease in Gini coefficient score (Table 1).

These models were then rerun using predicted climatic data to visualize shifts in the spatial distributions of suitable kelp habitat in decade increments starting in 2020 and going until 2100. We selected three distinct climate scenarios (Choi et al., 2025), SSP, to capture a range of potential climate futures in increasing order of emissions and predicted warming: SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, and SSP5-8.5. To analyze changes in the species' distribution, we focused on the shifts of suitable habitat and geographic bounds, which we defined as pixels predicted as suitable across all 100 model iterations (Figure 13). For the final decade (2090-2100), we summed all three climate scenarios that were suitable kelp habitats across all 300 model iterations to identify potential refugia areas ([LINK TO R PROGRAM](#)).

Here we define a pixel as a square, in our case one approximately 9.26 km on a side, whose size is determined by the resolution of our environmental data. In terms of predicting suitable kelp habitat, a pixel calculated as being suitable is not predicted to be covered by kelp but rather that at least one kelp is predicted as being likely to survive within its area.

For each kelp species, the model produced a raster, that is a pixelated map, for each decade of the modeling period indicating how many of the 100 model iterations met our suitable habitat criteria (Figures 1-8). Using ArcGIS Pro 3.5.0

software each raster cell for these model output maps was first filtered to retain only areas with less than 60m average ocean depth, as determined by the Bio-Oracle bathymetry layer (Assis et al., 2024), and where at least one model iteration predicted suitable habitat.

For visualization purposes these raster pixels were then converted to points, with each point was then buffered by 0.1km and classified into 10 equal-interval classes using the yellow-blue Viridis graduated color scheme. Using ArcGIS Pro 3.5.0 software, for each kelp species in the refugia maps (Figures 14-18), raster cells that contained suitable modeled habitat for each and every model iteration were selected. For display purposes, each of these raster cells was converted to a point feature, which was then buffered by 0.05km. buffered areas of nearby raster cells overlap to form polygons. Additionally, data layers for NOAA Aquaculture Opportunity Areas (AOA) (Morris et al., 2024), and California MPAs (Marine Region GIS, 2025), were rendered alongside the refugia locations (Figure 16 & 17).

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3.3 Findings

For the present day models dated 2010-2020, there are variables important in both the giant kelp and the bull kelp models. For bull kelp and giant kelp, the ten most important variables are recorded in the following table (Table 1). For giant kelp, the model accuracy has a mean TSS score of 0.970 +/- 0.008. For bull kelp, the model accuracy has a mean TSS of 0.962 +/- 0.017. In both cases we can safely state that our kelp SDMs are highly accurate.

The most likely suitable areas for giant kelp habitat, for the period 2010-2020, were found along the central California coast and within the southern California bight, particularly around the Channel Islands (Figure 1).

Another large, contiguous area of highly suitable giant kelp habitat is predicted along the central coast, with strong concentrations around the Monterey Peninsula and extending south along the Big Sur coastline. For bull kelp, for the period 2010-2020, the likeliest habitat area stretches from the Oregon border south along the coast of northern California (Figure 2).

The most likely suitable areas for giant kelp habitat, for the period 2010-2020, were found along the central California coast and within the southern California bight, particularly around the Channel Islands (Figure 1).

Giant Kelp		Bull Kelp	
Variable Name	Rank	Variable Name	Rank
Chlorophyll	1	Bathymetry [seaFloor]	1
Bathymetry [seaFloor]	2	Average Diffuse Attenuation Coefficient	2
Phytoplankton	3	Total Cloud Fraction	3
Silicate	4	Phosphate	4
OceanTemperature [min]	5	MixedLayerDepth	5
MixedLayerDepth	6	Chlorophyll	6
OceanTemperature	7	pH	7
Nitrate	8	Nitrate	8
OceanTemperature [max]	9	Phytoplankton	9
OceanTemperature [depthMax]	10	OceanTemperature [depthMax]	10

TABLE 1: Rank importances of top ten variables to each Species Distribution Model. Each variable was detailing at [depthSurf] & [mean] unless otherwise stated

Our results highlight the possibility of a northward trend in suitable habitat for both species.

A QUICK GUIDE TO INTERPRETING SDM & CLIMATE PATHWAYS

How to understand a Species Distribution Model (SDM).

Figure A: An example amalgamation of 100 model runs of a species distribution model.

As you may be aware, depending on your local climate, forecasting is fundamentally uncertain. We never seem to be able to predict exactly when or how much it may rain! Trying to predict future kelp habitats is just challenging. So, just like with weather forecasts, we run models many times to help build a more accurate picture. Each model run in turn helps us reduce the impact of random noise and model errors, allowing us to infer that if a habitat shows up in 90% or more (shown above in yellow), it is quite likely to be a suitable habitat for that species.

What is a Shared Socioeconomic Pathway and why consider multiple?

Figure B: The process that undertaken when defining the IPCC's five SSPs.

The future shared socioeconomic pathway humanity collectively undertakes is still uncertain. To better anticipate how canopy-forming kelp may migrate, we selected 3 pathways.

PREDICTED SUITABLE KELP HABITAT (2010 - 2020)

M. pyrifera habitat California 2010-2020

Figure 1: Suitable habitat predicted for *M. pyrifera* in California for 2010-2020.

The most likely suitable areas for *M. pyrifera* habitat for the period 2010-2020 were found along the Central California coast and within the Southern California Bight.

N. luetkeana habitat California 2010-2020

Figure 2: Suitable habitat predicted for *N. luetkeana* in California for 2010-2020.

For *N. luetkeana*, for the period 2010-2020, the likeliest habitat area stretches from the Oregon border south along the coast of Northern California.

Macrocystis pyrifera

Nereocystis luetkeana

MIDDLE WAY (SSP126) PATHWAY 2090 - 2100

M. pyrifera habitat California
2090-2100

Figure 3: Suitable habitat map predicted for *M. pyrifera* under SSP1-2.6 for 2090 - 2100.

N. luetkeana habitat California
2090-2100

Figure 4: Suitable habitat map predicted for *N. luetkeana* under SSP1-2.6 for 2090 - 2100.

Macrocyctis pyrifera

Nereocystis luetkeana

ROCKY ROAD (SSP245) PATHWAY 2090 - 2100

M. pyrifera habitat California
2090-2100

Figure 5: Suitable habitat map predicted for *M. pyrifera* under SSP2-4.5 for 2090 - 2100

N. luetkeana habitat California
2090-2100

Figure 6: Suitable habitat map predicted for *N. luetkeana* under SSP2-4.5 for 2090 - 2100.

Macrocystis pyrifera

Nereocystis luetkeana

FOSSIL FUELED (SSP585) PATHWAY 2090 - 2100

M. pyrifera habitat California
2090-2100

Figure 7: Suitable habitat map predicted for *M. pyrifera* under SSP5-8.5 for 2090 - 2100

N. luetkeana habitat California
2090-2100

Figure 8: Suitable habitat map predicted for *N. luetkeana* under SSP5-8.5 for 2090 - 2100

Macrocystis pyrifera

Nereocystis luetkeana

Maximal East Extent vs. Decade by Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) for *N. luetkeana*

Maximal South Extent vs. Decade by Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) for *N. luetkeana*

Figure 9: Graphs of the Maximal East and South extent shifts in geographic bounds by future shared socioeconomic pathways (SSP) over time for *N. luetkeana*. The north and west extent shifts in geographic bounds by future shared socioeconomic pathways (SSP) are omitted because they do not change over time for *N. luetkeana*.

Maximal West Extent vs. Decade by Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) for *M. pyrifera*

Maximal East Extent vs. Decade by Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) for *M. pyrifera*

Figure 10: Graphs of the Maximal West, and East extent shifts in geographic bounds by future shared socioeconomic pathways (SSP) over time for *M. pyrifera*.

Maximal North Extent vs. Decade by Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) for *M. pyrifera*

Figure 11 : Graph of the Maximal North extent shifts in geographic bounds by future shared socioeconomic pathways (SSP) over time for *M. pyrifera*.

Maximal South Extent vs. Decade by Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) for *M. pyrifera*

Figure 12: Graphs of the Maximal South extent shifts in geographic bounds by future shared socioeconomic pathways (SSP) over time for *M. pyrifera*.

Pixels vs. Decade by Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) for *N. luetkeana*

Pixels vs. Decade by Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) for *M. pyrifera*

Figure 13: Graphs of the shift in the number of pixels marked as suitable habitat in 100/100 models over time by future climate models for *M. pyrifera* and *N. luetkeana*, illustrating a downward shift of suitable habitat in the future.

For the refugia locations for bull kelp, the model predicts a slight northward contraction of suitable habitat (Figure 15). The most southerly climate refugia are confined to the eastern waters of the southern California bight (Figure 17). The bull kelp will generally be unsuited to future climatic conditions in Southern California.

For the refugia locations for giant kelp, significant areas of suitable habitat are predicted to remain around the Channel Islands and along the mainland coast (Figure 14). A major stronghold is expected to persist along the coast from Monterey Bay south through Big Sur (Figure 16).

M. pyrifera Refugia and MPAS 2090 - 2100

Figure 14 : Refugia distance map to Marine Protection Area (MPAs) for *M. pyrifera* in California for 2090 - 2100.

N. luetkeana Refugia and MPAS 2090 - 2100

Figure 15 : Refugia distance map to Marine Protection Area (MPAs) for *N. luetkeana* in California for 2090 - 2100.

N. luetkeana Refugia and MPAS 2090 - 2100

Figure 17 : Marine Protection Area (MPAs) and Refugia map for *N. luetkeana* in Southern California for 2090 - 2100

M. pyrifera Refugia and MPAS 2090 - 2100

Figure 16 : Marine Protection Area (MPAs) and Refugia map for *M. pyrifera* in Southern California for 2090 - 2100..

Figure 18 : AOs and Refugia map colored by their area of interest to *M.pyrifera* and *N. luetkeana* in Southern California for 2090 - 2100.

Another large, contiguous area of highly suitable giant kelp habitat is predicted along the central coast, with strong concentrations around the Monterey Peninsula and extending south along the Big Sur coastline. For bull kelp, for the period 2010-2020, the likeliest habitat area stretches from the Oregon border south along the coast of northern California (Figure 2).

Each decade's data was exported as a static image and stitched into an animation using Photoshop. The animation illustrates the suitable habitat of each climate scenario for each kelp species from 2010 to 2100 (LINK TO TABLE).

Future climate scenarios predict a retraction of bull kelp from the Channel Islands and Los Angeles (LINK TO TABLE). A modest northward range shift is also anticipated for the suitable habitats of bull kelp (Figure 15). While bull kelp is projected to be present along the northern Californian coast, the species is projected to recede from waters south of the southern California bight. This indicates a diminishment of suitable habitat for bull kelp in central or southern California.

Our results indicate that suitable habitats for giant kelp are projected to diminish in size (Figure 13), yet several key areas are anticipated to endure (Figures 3-8). The most prominent remaining hotspots are located in central California, specifically the region encompassing Monterey Bay and the Big Sur coast, which is predicted to remain a significant stronghold for giant kelp. Another remaining area of predicted suitable habitat is within the southern California bight, where substantial patches of suitable habitat are expected to persist around the Channel Islands and along the Los Angeles coastline.

In both our models, bathymetry (depth) was an important variable (Table 1). However, our bull kelp model exhibited some probable over-fitting, with occurrences modeled into water with average depths greater than 100m, twice as deep than the deepest habitat of the species in California (Young et al., 2016; Selgrath et al., 2024). Thus a post-processing bathymetry mask was applied to both models to limit the habitat extend to water no deeper than 100m on average.

Additionally, the biological significance of certain important variables such as average diffuse attenuation coefficient, phosphate, and ocean temperature at max depth was well represented in the literature (Labbé et al., 2024, Roleda & Hurd, 2019). However, other variables such as chlorophyll concentration, mixed layer depth (The depth at which seawater mixes from wind and currents), and phytoplankton concentration are more likely to be correlated with other, more significant biogeological drivers such as nitrogen supply. (Goes et al., 2000, Jacox et al., 2024).

The geographic shifts for giant kelp illustrate a significant projected geographic shift of its habitat from 2020 to 2100 across different climate scenarios. The maximal northern and southern boundaries both show a northward trend in latitude, indicating a definitive northward shift of the entire habitat range. Concurrently, the maximal eastern and western boundaries display a westward trend in longitude, meaning the suitable habitat is also expected to move westward and further offshore.

The graphs plotting suitable habitat from 2020 to 2100 project a reduction in the total available area for both bull and giant kelp (Figures 13). The habitat suitability maps and graphs for bull kelp show a significant and steep decrease in the areas designated as suitable habitat over time (Figures 1-8). Collectively, these graphs indicate a future where the overall geographic footprint for both keystone kelp species is expected to shrink (Figures 1-8).

Given the importance of giant kelp and bull kelp in providing ecosystem services, the most southerly refugia areas of each species may be of particular interest in protecting (Eger et al., 2023). In all of the 300 runs of our 2090-2100 model, Giant kelp was predicted to persist in the Santa Monica Bay. Similarly, bull kelp was predicted to remain present in the Santa Barbara Channel.

3.5 Conclusions and recommendations

Our study investigated how, under several future climate scenarios, the distribution of suitable habitats for giant kelp and bull kelp were predicted to shift northwards along the California coast (Figures 1-8). As our results highlight the possibility of a northward trend in habitat for both species, this suggests a potential reduction of suitable habitat areas for both species under future climatic conditions in California. Furthermore, climate models with a greater atmospheric concentration of CO₂ displayed a greater reduction to the extent of both species.

It is important to note before assaying the results of our modelling that there are inherent uncertainties when modeling future ecosystems (Payne et al., 2015). Our model predicts geographic shifts that suggest a significant northward contraction of the overall habitat range for bull kelp, with its southern boundaries retreating and its eastern, nearshore extent pulling back westward toward the sea (Figures 1-8). The magnitude of this shift varies depending on the climate scenario, with more extreme emissions scenarios resulting in more significant changes. This aligns with predictions that bull kelp will retract from southern and central California. It is important to note that our sample occur-

rence data is not a complete representation of the geographic distribution of kelp in California (Robinson et al., 2017). As such a potential improvement for future work may include the utilization of remotely sensed distribution of Californian kelp species, though difficulties currently persist in distinguishing giant kelp from bull kelp at relevant scales (Bell et al., 2023). Additionally, other modelling approaches, such as MAXENT, could be explored and the veracity of multiple models could be compared to select the model of best-fit (Robinson et al., 2017).

Particularly, for model improvements, future work may also wish to include important biotic factors such as the overabundance of purple sea urchins. Data currently exists on their occurrence, but it would require additional modeling techniques to convert such data into a form which could be readily incorporated in our SDMs (Klaassen et al., 2025; Eger et al., 2025).

Ultimately, limitations in our chosen approach and data result in our model being unable to capture certain biogeologically relevant processes. One significant example, due to the relatively coarse temporal resolution in our environmental input data, was that the potential effects of marine heatwaves were not modeled. Previous work has identified marine heatwaves as a key factor influencing the abundance of both kelp species in California (Perez-Navarro et al., 2022; Michaud et al., 2022; Cavanaugh et al., 2019).

Notably, especially on relatively small spatial scales, Earth System Models such as Sixth Phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP6) which our Bio-Oracle v3.0 data was based may miss changes in localized ocean dynamics, resulting in significant differences in the mean conditions of any particular point on our data (Pereira et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2022; Assis et al., 2024). Furthermore, biotic adaptations already noted in the kelp diaspora such as adaptations to sea surface temperature cannot be accounted for in our model (Giraldo-Ospina et al., 2025).

As such, future work would benefit modelling areas of particular interest as smaller spatial and temporal scales, with biotic elements, and utilizing alternative modelling approaches such as numerical ocean circulation models to create an

important, higher resolution data set (Klaassen et al., 2025).

Additionally, we caveat that a more fine-grained climate modelling is warranted to validate these results; especially with regards to modeling kelp habitat suitability in areas with multiple stakeholders and interests. Our recommendation in regards to refugia and existing MPAs, our model results for both species overlap with the Point Buchon MPA near Morro Bay, CA. A site that is already notable for its extensive kelp beds (CDFW, 2025). As such, we would also recommend the potential significance of this site as a refugia for both kelp species.

Similarly, in respect to the NOAA AOA, bull kelp may be better suited for cultivation in the long term to the Santa Barbara Channel AOA, while giant kelp could potentially be farmed in the Santa Monica Bay AOA over the coming century.

The natural ability of kelp populations to adapt to changing climatic conditions through genetic variation is an area for further research study (Young et al., 2025). A limitation of the study is

that future projections do not account for likely alterations in ocean currents (Young et al., 2025). Therefore, how future changes in hydrodynamics will impact kelp distribution and connectivity is not fully known (Young et al., 2025).

The study did not incorporate species interactions, such as overgrazing by urchins, into the models because of a lack of sufficient continuous data (Young et al., 2025). However, kelp seems to be resilient to warmer temperatures if nutrient availability remains high (Giraldo-Ospina et al., 2025). Local processes and adaptations may be more impactful in future climates (Giraldo-Ospina et al., 2025).

Dispersal trajectories driven by oceanographic transport were not considered, potentially creating inconsistencies between projected and realized future expansions where major oceanographic barriers play a role (Choi, 2025). The effectiveness of using novel restoration approaches in these areas, such as transplanting kelp from warmer, climate-adapted provenances, is not yet known and requires further investigation (Young et al., 2025).

PHOTO : TAYLOR GRIFFITH

Policy

Authors : Zahra Amir, Naomie Martinez, Charlie Mitchell

4.1 Introduction

Environmental policy plays a critical role in shaping how societies protect and manage ecosystems.

By establishing regulatory frameworks, directing funding, and coordinating institutions, policy provides both safeguards against ecological degradation and pathways toward restoration. In the marine context, environmental policies determine how natural resources and impacts are assessed. Policy also determines how restoration projects are implemented; making governance a cornerstone for ecological recovery (Shumway et al., 2021; Bell-James, Foster, and Shumway, 2023).

California has long been recognized as a leader in environmental governance (Cleveland, 2024). Over the course of more than a century, the state has developed a comprehensive and ambitious system of laws and institutions designed to protect its land, freshwater, and marine environments (Cleveland, 2024). This legacy has ensured strong protections for coastal resources, but it has also created a complex and, at times, challenging regulatory environment in terms of compliance for coastal projects such as kelp forest restoration and aquaculture (Cleveland, 2024).

The layered nature of California’s environmental policy reflects the state’s history of conservation leadership and the challenges of coordinating across multiple agencies, stakeholders, and legal mandates.

These regulatory difficulties are particularly frustrating given the vast untapped potential of better management of kelp forests in California. Kelp forests provide essential ecosystem services, including sequestering carbon, buffering against ocean acidification, supporting fisheries, and enhancing coastal resilience (Eger et al., 2022).

Kelp restoration and aquaculture efforts are also inherently dependent on governance structures that enable access to coastal areas, ensure ecological safeguards, and align local initiatives with broader climate and biodiversity goals. Without supportive policy, projects can stall due to financial, procedural, and institutional barriers; with it, they can scale effectively to meet urgent environmental challenges (Eger et al., 2020; Rubino, 2023). In this way, ecological policy functions not simply as a regulatory backdrop but as a decisive factor in the future of kelp forest recovery and sustainable marine development.

How will policy uplift restoration efforts?

4.2 Methods

This study employed a multi-pronged approach to assess the policy and governance dimensions of kelp restoration and aquaculture in California. First, we conducted a broad literature review of peer-reviewed articles, policy reports, and legal analyses on kelp restoration, aquaculture regulation, and environmental governance. This review drew from ecological sciences, marine policy, and political science, allowing us to capture both the technical and institutional challenges of restoration (Baker, Eckerberg, and Zachrisson, 2014; Shumway et al., 2021; Bell-James, Foster, and Shumway, 2023). Particular attention was given to studies addressing the role of financial and institutional support in enabling restoration at scale (Eger et al., 2020) and global syntheses that evaluate lessons learned from more than two centuries of kelp restoration efforts worldwide (Eger et al., 2022).

Second, we undertook a comparative case analysis of kelp governance frameworks in California, Hawaii, and Maine. Maine has developed a relatively streamlined system for managing coastal resources, emphasizing ecosystem-based management through spatial planning, harvest limits, and habitat restoration initiatives (Cornelisen, 1998). In contrast, Hawaii integrates cultural stewardship and community co-management into its restoration strategies, embedding Indigenous knowledge and local participation into forest and coastal restoration programs (Friday et al., 2015). By contrasting these approaches with California's fragmented permitting system, we identified transferable lessons for designing more efficient, equitable, and ecologically grounded governance structures (Cleveland, 2024).

Finally, we conducted a detailed mapping of California's current regulatory environment to identify the major permits, agencies, and procedures involved in kelp forest restoration and aquaculture. This analysis included state-level frameworks such as the California Environmental Quality Act (CEQA), the California Coastal Act, and the Marine Life Protection Act, alongside federal overlays including the Clean Water Act and the National Environmental Policy Act

(NEPA). Recent studies by Cleveland (2024) and Silverman-Roati, Webb, and Gerrard (2022) were particularly valuable in tracing procedural bottlenecks and highlighting where interagency coordination remains limited. Together, these methods provided a comprehensive foundation for evaluating both the obstacles and opportunities within California's policy landscape.

4.3 Findings

One of the biggest obstacles to the advancement of restoration and aquaculture projects in California is the complicated permitting process. Projects often require approvals from a wide range of agencies, including the California Coastal Commission, State Lands Commission, California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW), California State Water Resources Control Board, and, at the federal level, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) and the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers. Each agency enforces its own criteria, timelines, and documentation requirements, which rarely align with those of other agencies.

Furthermore, projects frequently need to apply for several overlapping permits (**Table 1**), including a Coastal Development Permit from the State Water Board, a General Lease of Sovereign Lands from the State Lands Commission, a Clean Water Act Water Quality Certification from the State Water Board, and a Scientific Collecting Permit from CDFW. For aquaculture, additional approvals such as an Aquaculture Registration or a Private Lands Aquaculture Permit may be necessary, further complicating the process.

This highly scattered framework discourages innovation and delays critically needed restoration projects by making the process time-consuming and expensive. Researchers and industry stakeholders face considerable uncertainty in the absence of a centralized or efficient permitting system. Ultimately, this prolonged process slows the progress in kelp restoration and sustainable aquaculture development.

One of the biggest obstacles to the advancement of restoration and aquaculture projects in California is the complicated permitting process.

Table 1: California and Federal Agencies

Agencies	Purpose
Ocean Protection Council (OPC)	Protects California's coast and oceans by implementing science-based policies and management, fostering partnerships, collaborations, and investments.
California Coastal Commission (CCC)	Protects California's coast and ocean through planning and regulation.
California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW)	Implements and enforces regulations set by the Fish and Game Commission, and provides biological data and expertise to inform the decision-making process.
California Natural Resources Agency (CNAR)	Oversees and supports more than 26 departments, conservancies, and commissions. Protects, manages, and restores the environment and its natural, cultural, and historical resources.
Fish and Game Commission (FGC)	Forms general policies, controls seasons, bag limits, regulates hunting/fishing, establishes and regulates protected lands/waters, and MPAs.
Army Corps of Engineers	Protects and restores ecosystems, manages hazardous, toxic, or radioactive waste, reduces risks from disasters by creating storm damage reduction infrastructure, sustains waterways, and provides recreation opportunities at lakes and marinas.
National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)	Holds key leadership in shaping international ocean, fisheries, climate, space, and weather policies. They have research programs, vessels, satellites, science centers, and laboratories
California Environmental Protection Agency (CalEPA)	Develops, implements, and enforces environmental policies/laws that regulate air, water, and soil quality.
California State Lands Commission (SLC)	Manages 4 million acres of waterways, protects state waters from marine invasive species, prevents oil spills by regulating oil transfers, and is a leader in fighting against climate change and transitioning away from fossil fuels to clean energy.

Table 2: Permits in California

Permitting requirements for kelp restoration often include a combination of scientific collection permits, habitat restoration approvals, water quality certifications, and aquaculture leases, many of which necessitate coordination between state and federal agencies (Cleveland, 2024). This layering of permits increases costs, prolongs timelines, and limits participation by smaller community-led initiatives. Research stresses that such regulatory hurdles are among the most consistent inhibitors of scaling restoration efforts worldwide (Cleveland, 2024; Bell-James, Foster, and Shumway, 2023). Table 2, shown below, provides a list of permits, along with their purpose and the authority issuing them.

Permit Type	Purpose / Activities Covered	Issuing Authority
Scientific Collecting Permit (SCP)	Authorizes the collection of marine organisms for research; prohibits the reintroduction of specimens to the wild post-experimentation	California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW)
Restoration Permit	Allows outplanting, habitat enhancement, or other restoration interventions in marine environments	CDFW (may also require coordination with State Lands Commission and California Coastal Commission)
Aquaculture Lease / Permit	Grants rights to cultivate kelp or other seaweeds for commercial or restoration purposes	California State Lands Commission; California Coastal Commission; National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) for federal waters
Section 404 / 401 Clean Water Act Permits	Regulates the discharge of fill material into U.S. waters and certifies compliance with water quality standards	U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (404); California State Water Resources Control Board (401)
Endangered Species Act (ESA) Consultation	Ensures restoration activities do not harm listed species or critical habitat	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service; NOAA Fisheries
Coastal Development Permit (CDP)	Required for most development, restoration, or aquaculture projects within the coastal zone	California Coastal Commission

Table 3: Non-profit support and Funding Opportunities

A variety of state, federal, and nonprofit organizations provide critical funding and partnership opportunities for marine restoration and coastal resilience efforts in California. These funders support projects ranging from kelp forest recovery to community engagement. Table 3 highlights key partners, their areas of focus, and the types of support they offer.

Funder/Partner	Focus	Support Type
California Sea Grant	Marine research, coastal ecosystems, and aquaculture	Grant
NOAA	Habitat restoration, marine ecosystems, climate resilience	Grant / Cooperative Agreements
California Ocean Protection Council	Ocean health, coastal resilience, restoration projects	State Grant
California State Coastal Conservancy	Habitat restoration, climate adaptation, coastal protection	California Department of Fish and Wildlife
California State Water Resources Control Board	Water quality, stormwater management, and the disadvantaged community	Grants & Low-Interest Loans (CWSRF, WRFP, SAFER Program)
Ocean Conservancy	Ocean advocacy, restoration, and climate resilience	Grants / Partnerships
The Bay Foundation	Kelp forest restoration, community engagement	Direct Project Partnerships
Heal the Bay	Water quality, coastal restoration, community engagement, kelp education	Community Programs

California can significantly improve its kelp restoration practices by adopting kelp management strategies from other U.S. states, specifically those found in Maine and Hawaii. Maine in particular has demonstrated the potential to become a global leader in sustainable seaweed harvesting and management. With nearly 3,500 miles of rocky coastline along the Gulf of Maine, the state supports a variety of kelp and seaweed species, including bladderwrack, rockweed, sugar kelp, sea lettuce, Irish moss, and dulce (Webber et al., 2020). In 2020 alone, 8,165 tons of wild and farmed seaweed were harvested, with a value of about \$1.6 million USD (Webber et al., 2020). Within the last 5 years, approximately 125 harvesting permits have been issued each year within Maine (Webber et al., 2020).

Maine has also implemented an ecosystem-based management plan which prioritizes a blue economy that is socially equitable and environmentally sustainable (Webber et al., 2020).

Using strategies such as spatial management of aquaculture plots, harvest and bycatch limits, gear restrictions, and other strategies to protect sensitive wildlife areas and encourage kelp regeneration, Maine provides an excellent framework that California can incorporate into its own restoration and management policies.

Hawaii also provides a great model for California, with its long standing social, cultural, and economic ties to kelp. The Hawaiian Islands are home to over 522 species of macroalgae, 83% of which are native, and carry rich cultural significance. Collectively known as limu, a Hawaiian term for a plant growing in a wet place, these seaweeds have been a regular part of the local community's diet for centuries, serving as spices and vegetables (McDermid et al., 2019). Seaweeds were also used for medicinal purposes, in commerce as valuable items, and even for adornments during ceremonies (McDermid et al., 2019). Unlike Maine or California, who rely on permitting for kelp management, Hawaii em-

PHOTO : TAYLOR GRIFFITH

phasizes cultural stewardship and local engagement. Many communities actively participate in restoring native species of seaweeds through replanting, removal of invasive macroalgae, and preserving traditional knowledge (Nelson et al., 2018). California can embed these cultural and indigenous practices into its current kelp management systems in order to facilitate increased local engagement and inclusivity in restoration.

By applying Maine's regulatory model and incorporating Hawaii's cultural values into its own restoration strategies, California can build a kelp management system that is ecologically sustainable, socially inclusive, and successful in the long-term.

4.4 Conclusions and recommendations

This research highlights that, while California has long been a leader in environmental governance, the current permitting landscape for kelp forest restoration and aquaculture remains fragmented, costly, and time-consuming (Cleveland 2024; Bell-James, Foster, and Shumway 2023). Complex regulatory requirements spread across multiple agencies create delays that hinder urgent ecological recovery, despite clear benefits to the climate and biodiversity that come from restoring kelp ecosystems (Eger et al., 2020; Eger et al., 2022). At the same time, comparative insights from Maine and Hawaii demonstrate that more streamlined, community-driven, and ecosystem-based approaches can accelerate progress while ensuring ecological safeguards and equity (Cleveland, 2024). Effective policy is therefore not only a protective measure but also a critical enabler of large-scale kelp restoration, climate resilience, and sustainable aquaculture (Rubino, 2023; Shumway et al., 2021).

To move forward, we recommend the following reforms:

Establish a dedicated marine restoration permitting pathway that reduces redundancy and expedites review processes (Bell-James, Foster, and Shumway 2023; Cleveland 2024); create a statewide permitting hub offering comprehensive and publicly accessible guidance (Shumway et al. 2021); and develop a GIS-based permit and agency map to increase transparency across jurisdictions (Cleveland 2024).

Legislative amendments should codify streamlined permitting and coordinated management (Silverman-Roati, Webb, and Gerrard, 2022), while ensuring that dedicated staff positions and cross-agency restoration teams are in place to support implementation (Eger et al., 2020). Finally, California should integrate Ecosystem-Based Management (EBM) and Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM) principles directly into its statutory and regulatory frameworks, drawing on the successful examples of Maine and Hawaii (Eger et al., 2022; Cleveland, 2024).

Together, these reforms can transform policy from a bottleneck into a catalyst, enabling kelp restoration to play its full role in advancing climate goals, protecting biodiversity, and supporting coastal communities in California.

PHOTO : TAYLOR GRIFFITH

Kelp restoration and aquaculture efforts are also inherently dependent on governance structures that enable access to coastal areas, ensure ecological safeguards, and align local initiatives with broader climate and biodiversity goals. Without supportive policy, projects can stall due to financial, procedural, and institutional barriers; with it, they can scale effectively to meet urgent environmental challenges.

(Eger et al. 2020; Rubino 2023)

PHOTO : TAYLOR GRIFFITH

Science Communication

Authors : Joy Herzberger, Karli Klein, Maps Rasmussen, Zee Zetino

Editor's note:

Science, according to the philosopher Karl Popper, is the process of proposing and testing falsifiable statements. What then happens with the results of these tests, what are the implications of these results, and how can meaning be communicated from them? In this section the authors explored alternative ways to engage audiences beyond the scientific community. Drawing from the arts, media, and social sciences, they aimed to build broader public knowledge and support for kelp restoration along the California coastline. They also explored the even more fundamental question of what ecological 'restoration' even means in the ever-evolving context of the living world. Reexamining the ideas associated with ecological 'restoration' in social, cultural, and ethical contexts, as well the terms and frameworks which shape our relationship with the natural world. Investigations were also given to the role of AI, mapping, and art in helping to connect the practice of science to larger communities. Additional thought was also paid to the role of indigenous practices and philosophies in guiding efforts at ecological 'restoration' and the role of human beings as ecological stewards.

5.1 Introduction

How do we get people to care—and act? In this section we explore kelp forest restoration through interdisciplinary approaches, including art, media, cultural analysis, storytelling, and linguistic inquiry. Acknowledging that the climate crisis requires strategies that go beyond data and policy, this chapter addresses ways to shape understanding and enable meaningful participation across different communities.

Effective communication must consider how knowledge is conveyed, the assumptions embedded in language, and the historical frameworks that shape interpretation of restoration and ecological change. Terms such as restoration carry implicit ideas of stability, progress, and loss. However, in dynamic ecosystems, restoration often involves negotiating ongoing change rather than returning to a fixed baseline.

Restoration is understood not only as ecological recovery, but as the renewal of relationships, practices, and memories; all of these together help connect human communities to coastal ecosystems. Situating kelp forests within human histories frames restoration as a dialogue between science and society, extending beyond species or ecosystem management to include cultural, ethical, and social dimensions.

Media and the arts provide complementary tools for engagement: Visual media, storytelling, and participatory projects extend communication to broader audiences, contextualizing ecological knowledge in a culturally meaningful way and combining scientific research with public understanding and action.

With the integration of both technical and cultural dimensions, these interdisciplinary approaches enhance the effectiveness and equity of restoration efforts. More importantly, by combining ecological knowledge with ethical, social, and cultural considerations, diverse communities can engage with restoration efforts in a more meaningful and impactful way.

How do we
get people to
care and to
act?

EDITOR'S NOTE:

The following essay investigates what the meaning of loss in ecology means in light of the ever-dynamic living world. How do we describe what loss even means in the context of kelp forests? Here ideas on the language of loss, and more broadly the nature of language itself as it pertains to the living world and human societies, are discussed. How have human societies described their role in relation to the larger living world, and can that language of relationships shift the behaviors of modern industrial societies from being purely extractive of kelp forests to long-term stewards?

FEELING CRISIS

Close observation in nature was my first science—an initiation into ecology, the web of relationships it describes, and loss, long before I had the language to describe it. Words came later. First there was noticing, feeling, understanding through the body. Spoken language arises from these tangible encounters and they can either deepen or distance our experience with land. Each summer and winter, I returned to the same coastline with tidepools erupting with a psychedelic array of life. My father offered a quarter for every sea star I found. I counted, compared, and noticed. My body memorized the rhythm of the sea long before I had words like “wave action” or “current.”

When sea star wasting disease hollowed out the pools, I felt the loss before I understood its ecology. Later, swimming tangled in kelp beneath the night sky, I saw forests thinning during the marine heatwave known as the Blob. Not only did I earn fewer quarters; I learned ecological grief—watching a crisis unfold in real time.

Care begins with attention. To speak differently is to care differently. Environmental knowledge emerges through observation, not declaration. The decline of bull kelp along the northern California coast, the effects of warming waters, the loss of biodiversity - these are not stories found in data alone. They are learned by looking, touching, remembering.

**Kelp drifts, bends,
releases, adapts.
Watching it is a lesson
in entanglement. To
understand, you must
be inside it: your hands
brushed by its fronds,
your legs tangled, your
breath exchanged with
the sea.**

Measuring kelp forest loss in cubic meters distances it; describing the collapse of homes restores gravity. Forests are processes, conversations, encounters. You learn nature through sensation, through intimacy, through noticing. Language names what the body has already known. To care is to attend to what the body knows.

DO YOU LISTEN TO THE LAND ?

When I walk a forest path or swim in kelp with otters, I am being watched. The world does not begin when I enter; it is already unfolding. Language is much larger than human speech: the howl of the wind, the feeling of moss, the glistening of seaweed.

Deep ecology teaches that all beings have intrinsic value, not for what they provide us, but in their own accord (Naess, 1973). All organisms in the living world, i.e. non human animals or algae, have culture, values, and knowledge outside of our own. (Haraway, 2008)

Language, then, begins with attention. It is an embodied expression, a mutual act of speaking and listening, a way to tell stories and hear them.

DIRECT ENCOUNTERS (WITH KELP FORESTS AND OTHER LIVING THINGS)

Direct encounters—swimming through kelp forests, touching sea stars—shape environmental awareness and conservation behavior. A person’s “personalized ecology,” the unique set of sensory experiences accumulated over a lifetime, forms the foundation of their relationship with nature (Louv, 2005). These sights, sounds, smells, textures, and patterns shape values and actions toward the living world (Berkes, 1999).

Yet direct experiences are declining, replaced by indirect encounters (seeing a forest from a car window) or mediated ones (watching a documentary). Louv (2005) calls this the “extinction of experience”—a loss driven by shrinking natural spaces and reduced human desire to engage with them.

This loss feeds “nature apathy,” increasingly common due to urbanization, screen-centered lives, and limited green access (Miller, 2005). It also fuels “shifting baseline syndrome,” in which each generation normalizes degraded ecosystems, eroding motivation for conservation (Soga & Gaston, 2021).

Our experiences with the living world shape how we care for it.

Access itself is unequally distributed. Low-income communities and communities of color often face structural barriers to green space (Byrne, 2012; Finney, 2014). In the Global North, Black, Latinx, and Indigenous urban communities confront systemic exclusion, while in the Global South, communities sustain daily ecological contact even as they disproportionately bear climate impacts (Escobar (1999); Carruthers (2008).

Yet modern environmentalism has historically centered white, middle-class communities, often overlooking that marginalized populations not only have limited access to green space but are also more likely to live in areas exposed to environmental hazards—oil wells, refineries, pesticide use, contaminated water, and other toxins—and lack the resources and infrastructure to prepare for or recover from extreme climate events (Sanders, 2025).

Our experiences with the living world shape how we care for it. Restoring ecosystems requires restoring people’s direct, meaningful connections to them—and by addressing the social and structural barriers that limit access. Care follows from experience; when nature is felt, touched, lived, a sense of responsibility deepens.

WHAT IS “NATURE” ?

“There is no such thing as nature. What we encounter instead is an infinite set of entanglements in which we are already caught” (Morton, 2007).

Kelp is not a thing but a continent: of slugs, worms, sea stars, otters, octopuses, microbes—and us. To enter a kelp forest is to lose one’s edges, to realize that the human body is not a self-contained unit but a site of constant exchange. As Stephen R. Palumbi observes, “Kelp forests live between land and sea, sun and darkness, movement and rootedness” (Palumbi, n.d.). They remind us that human life is also suspended in such thresholds, woven through wider ecologies of exchange. Stacy Alaimo calls this trans-corporeality: “the recognition that the environment is not ‘out there’—it is always the very substance of ourselves” (Alaimo, 2010).

Words have the power to distance us from the things they name. In Western thought, “**Nature**” has often been imagined as something separate from humans, a place “**out there.**” (Merchant, 1980; Daston & Park, 1998). It is a word that marks distance, functioning less as a description than as a boundary. But our bodies are not sealed containers; they absorb, exchange, and are composed of the lives around them. The challenge lies in unlearning this fiction of separation and learning instead to feel the truth of our entanglement.

This illusion of separation is held in place by Western language. Nature comes from the Greek *physis*, meaning “**to grow, to be,**” (Dear, 2006) and once described a world intimately entangled with us (Ducarme & Couvet, 2020). Natural philosophy bound observation, ethics, and wonder together. But the Scientific Revolution and its accompanying colonial vocabularies narrowed this expansive sense of being into numbers, laws, and resources (Merchant, 1980; Daston & Park, 1998).

Language facilitated this transformation: from living beings to usable things. This shift from animacy to resource is evident in the renaming of vibrant ecosystems. To call kelp a “**marine resource**” or “**natural capital**” collapses its “**aliveness**” into a commodity. Even the term “**kelp beds,**” once common, domesticates vast forests into units of human utility. Words build categories—alive/not alive, human/nonhuman, natural/unnatural—that shape what we see as valuable or worthy of protection.

Natural things, such as kelp, were framed in relation to what they provide for us: forests became timber, rivers became resources, kelp became a commodity.

In contrast, Indigenous vocabularies offer a path to repairing this forgotten kinship. In Anishinaabemowin, the word for nature, *inaandiziwin*, means “way of life,” (Kimmerer, 2013) refusing the distinction between human and nonhuman. Yanomami leader Davi Kopenawa calls mining scars “wounds of the forest” (Davi Kopenawa, 2022) and refers to climate change as “the revenge of the earth,” (Davi Kopenawa, 2022) giving agency to processes that Western vocabularies objectify. Robin Wall Kimmerer proposes a “grammar of animacy,” in which rivers and birds are spoken of as “someone,” not “something” (Kimmerer, 2017). Such practices of naming are more than poetic gestures; they are acts of ethical reorientation, restoring kinship and beginning the long process of healing our relationship with the world.

This re-evaluation of language is not a softening of scientific rigor but a broadening of its scope to include embodied and emotional truths. The words we choose have tangible consequences for conservation, policy, and our sense of responsibility. Research shows that naming stress and grief is itself a survival strategy.

A 2019 study found that the term “climate crisis” elicited a 60% stronger brain reaction than “climate change,” highlighting how a single word can shift perception and urgency (SPARK Neuro, 2019; Warner 2025). Calling people “citizens” rather than “consumers” increases responsibility (SPARK Neuro, 2019).

Arran Stibbe argues vocabularies are rarely neutral (Stibbe, 2018). They carry colonial and racialized residues, reinforce hierarchies, erase ecological agency, and privilege certain types of knowledge over others (Cheng et al., 2023). Terms such as “invasive species” or descriptors that label animals as “aggressive,” “dominant,” or “hypersexual” show how language encodes harmful assumptions and projects human social hierarchies onto nonhuman life (Stibbe, 2018). Projects like Bird Names for Birds and the Entomological Society of America’s Better Common Names Project intervene in these systems, re-naming species as an act of collective justice. This “communal justicing” does not weaken scientific rigor but expands it, creating space for more ethical ways of naming and knowing.

The Bureau of Linguistical Reality argues for inventing and reviving terms, such as *Solastalgia*, which names the grief for a degraded home, and *Koyaanisqatsi*, meaning “life out of balance,” (Bureau of Linguistical Reality 2014) which anchor emotional truth within the scientific record, acknowledging that our feelings are a valid part of ecological experience. They note that English often lacks the capacity to hold ecological complexity. The limits of our language are also the limits of our imagination.

NEW LANGUAGE OF CRISIS

To speak
differently
is to care
differently.

COLLAGE : MAPS RASMUSSEN

The Loss of a forest is the loss of a part of you

EDITOR'S NOTE:

What does grief mean with regards to something as dynamic and complex as a kelp forest? The following essay reflects on the idea that the intricate network of relationships governing a kelp forest contains its own intelligence. How do human beings relate to these intelligences, and what may come of the grief stemming from breaking reciprocal relationships between humanity and these ecosystems? What can we learn about our attempts at 'restoration' when we let go of ideas of loss in a static system?

LEARNING FROM KELP

Kelp teaches: to live is to bend, to release, and to be carried. Some of our best models for restoration come not from humans but from other species. Restoration is often imagined as a human endeavor: an attempt to repair, to return, to manage. But kelp resists such linearity. It teaches us that survival and renewal do not emerge from order or purity, but from entanglement.

When I first met kelp, its slimy fronds brushed against my skin. Its limbs bent and swayed around me, shaping the water as I moved through it. As ecologist Callum Roberts notes, "kelp defies monoculture. It refuses neat rows. It tangles. It touches. It ghosts across limbs and reefs" (Roberts, 2012). Survival in the ocean, like survival on land, depends on flexibility: letting go, holding others, bending with currents. Later I would learn the word resilience, but my first encounter with it was bodily.

Kelp does not resist change; it becomes it.

To imagine a kelp forest is to picture not just towering limbs but a bus stop in a restless city—a terminal where fish, invertebrates, microbial hitchhikers, and currents converge. Pneumatocysts keep fronds afloat; holdfasts cling to stone as waves pound by. Kelp does not resist change; it becomes it. It senses shifts in light, nutrients, temperature, and currents and remembers through its body. Older fronds let go

so new ones may grow. Its memory is not cognitive but material.

Kelp is an archive.

It tells a story of shifting coastlines shaped by industry and of resistance. It absorbs what we discard, reassembling carbon dioxide into oxygen, to give us breath again. As I write this sentence, I take a deep breath and imagine that it was first exhaled by algae. In this way, the sea and I keep each other alive.

Kelp reminds us that survival is relational.

Robin Wall Kimmerer writes, "Kelp does not dominate; it entangles" (Kimmerer, 2013). It models what Stacy Alaimo calls "trans-corporeality: a being that is always becoming with another" (Alaimo, 2010). Their bodies aren't isolated; they materially and biologically shape and are shaped by their surroundings and co-inhabitants.

A Kelp forest is a system of distributed Intelligence.

Detached blades form rafts carrying micro-ecosystems, crabs, bryozoans, nudibranchs, worms, that drift across oceans. Under the right conditions, kelp can grow two feet per day, forming canopies that buffer storms, redirect currents, and shelter hundreds of species. Otters nap in kelp's fronds, while their appetite for sea urchins keeps the forest in balance. Octopuses carve homes into its stipes, stirring nutrients along the forest floor. Whales rub against its body in a ritual of care, shedding parasites while clearing space for kelp to photosynthesize. Hydroids cling, feed, and in return offer protection. These exchanges, as Anna Tsing names them, constitute "collaborative survival": life sustained through overlapping interdependencies (Tsing, 2015).

Kelp models a different kind of Governance.

Kelp does not order through domination, but finds balance through reciprocity. Observing such systems can reframe restoration as a process of co-creation, in which human intervention is guided by the ecological wisdom already embedded in the living world, and kelp—its fronds and holdfasts tangled in currents—shows that to thrive in damaged environments is not to resist change, but to tangle with it.

H. NICKLIN, JR.

160 TIMES LIFE-SIZE

COLLAGE : MAPS RASMUSSEN

WHAT IS RESTORATION AND WHO GETS TO DECIDE?

Many restoration projects ask: **Can we go back?** These questions carry colonial fantasies of “wild” spaces imagined as empty and untouched by people. Mainstream restoration often relies on a “Pristine Reference State,” an imagined return to a pre-disturbed baseline (Jordan et al., 1987). Such frameworks erase millennia of Indigenous stewardship, collapsing complex ecologies into a single, fixed moment of “purity”. They erase the layered histories that shaped the land—the burns and blooms, the forced removals and massacres, centuries of tending and taking.

Conservation projects have often mirrored these systems of control. National parks like Yellowstone and Yosemite were declared “wild” only after forcibly removing Apsáalooke, Shoshone, and Miwok peoples. Species like the American bison were made “stable” only through enclosures after we nearly extirpated them. MPAs were often established without consulting Indigenous caretakers who had managed those same coastal areas for millennia.

As Michelle Murphy writes, “Restoration often becomes a scene of managing life in the aftermath, a mode of remaking environments and bodies in ways that reproduce the systems that harmed them” (Murphy, 2017).

Environmental protection is too often shaped by colonial systems of logic, where conservation becomes a tool of governance rather than a practice of care.

WHAT CAUSES ECOSYSTEMS TO COLLAPSE?

Environmental collapse is never the result of a single factor; it emerges from intersecting ecological, social, and political forces. Resource depletion, industrial extraction, pollution, cli-

mate disruption are layered over legacies of land theft, forced displacement, and colonial governance. These histories are not abstract—they are embedded in the land itself: in eroded soils, contaminated waterways, disappearing habitats, and in the absence of species. Landscapes carry memory: scars of controlled burns, deforestation, industrial expansion, agricultural runoff.

To restore an ecosystem without reading these histories is to erase the conditions that shaped it.

As Dylan Robinson writes, “**Settler colonialism is not in the past—it is sedimented into the land.**” (Robinson, 2018). These sediments are both literal and metaphorical: in pollutants and warming ocean waters, but also in the renaming of rivers, the drawing of borders, and the legal frameworks that govern access and control.

Listening to land means attending to both its ecological signals and its human histories.

The Capitalocene, as Jason W. Moore names our current era—is an ecological crisis produced by economic systems driven by inequalities of power and profit (Moore, 2015). Toxicity is not an accident; it has a geography. The same imperial fictions that divided “Nature” from “Culture” institutionalized the idea that some lives and lands are disposable. Ecocide—the deliberate killing of ecosystems—reveals environmental harm as inseparable from power, exploitation, and settler colonialism. Restoration efforts that fail to name these forces risk treating collapse as a purely biological problem rather than as a deeply human-made crisis

WHICH SPECIES MATTER?

The challenge of restoration lies in the friction between a simple fix and a complex reality. Culling sea urchins to protect kelp may allow kelp to rebound but can produce cascading ecological effects. Sea urchins are often framed as the primary villains in kelp loss, yet their ecological role is context-dependent; in barren states, urchins frequently lack nutritional value for native predators, and indiscriminate culling risks disrupting predator–prey dynamics, nutrient cycling, and benthic structure. Restoration requires considering both immediate goals and the impacts on the broader ecological web. (Filbee-Dexter et al., 2018)

Who decides which species matter? These decisions are rarely neutral; they are shaped by human values, cultural narratives, and aesthetic preferences (Heise, 2016). Human-centric biases privilege species perceived as valuable while overlooking others that are ecologically or culturally essential. Ursula K. Heise notes that “cultural narratives of extinction are not neutral, shaped by assumptions about beauty, heroism, and nostalgia” (Heise, 2016). Ethical restoration requires a holistic perspective: we must ask how interventions reshape the broader network and whose interests—human or nonhuman—guide them.

Underlying much of this history is a worldview that sees land primarily as a resource to extract from—a commodity to be owned, managed, and exploited. This extractive gaze reduces rich ecosystems to ‘natural capital,’ sidelining relational ways of knowing that honor reciprocity and interdependence over dominion. When land is seen only in terms of its utility — how much carbon it can store, how many species it can host, how many resources it can yield — we enact a settler form of violence (Merchant, 1980). This framing not only shapes restoration priorities but also limits the scope of what is imagined possible, but prioritizes economic efficiency over ecological integrity and social repair.

Restoration that fails to acknowledge the violences—ecological, cultural, epistemic—that shaped the “current” state becomes complicit in repeating them. It becomes a project of sorting: this belongs here, that does not; this species gets to live, that one does not.

The key question—“**What belongs here?**”—must always be followed by another: “**According to whom?**”

ECOLOGICAL NOSTALGIA AND FUTURALGIA

Ecological nostalgia—a longing for imagined past landscapes—tempts us with visions of return. As Svetlana Boym writes, nostalgia is “history without guilt,” a selective forgetting that smooths over violence and dispossession (Boym, 2001). Nostalgia can soften grief into passivity, longing into complicity (Reyes-Aldana, 2023). In the face of climate disruption, many ecosystems cannot return to pre-industrial or pre-colonial states. On the other hand, Futuralgia—the grief for futures that will never come—opens space to compost loss into new possibilities (Reyes-Aldana (2023). It acknowledges irreversible losses while holding imagination open. Restoration becomes a space for grieving, learning, and creating together within hybrid ecologies. As David Schlosberg observes, “**We might attend to memory not as a regression, but as a composting of what was, to nourish what might still become**” (Schlosberg, 2013).

The kelp forest is a record of survival, both its own and ours. Kelp shows us that life is always collaborative: it anchors, bends, breaks, and regrows. Its entanglements—fronds, otters, urchins, whales, microbes—mirror a justice-centered vision of restoration, one that embraces relationality and reciprocity. It centers Indigenous knowledge, frontline perspectives, and the rights of other species. By entwining ecological resilience with social repair, restoration can address environmental degradation and historical injustices. It becomes a collaboration with multi-species kin, holding histories of loss as a foundation for renewal, and nurturing what is and what might emerge.

To restore kelp is to restore relations: between humans and oceans, colonial histories and Indigenous futures, grief and resilience.

Ecologist
David Abram
said that
“climate change
is the simple
consequence of
forgetting the
holiness of this
mysterium in
which we’re
bodily
immersed.”

5.4 CONSIDERING ETHICS

EDITOR'S NOTE:

This essay takes the case study of efforts to restore sunflower sea star populations, which can be used to help restore kelp forests, as a way of illustrating the way outreach and research efforts can be successfully integrated. Ecological research can leverage public engagement to collect data as well as restore ecosystems. How then to best communicate these ideas in order to carry out such actions?

How much should humans intervene when it comes to ecological management, and on what basis should they make these decisions? Such information could come from ecologists and environmental scientists, but only about half of scientists are currently even engaged in public outreach (Zaelzer, 2020). A number of ecologists are not prioritizing communicating the value of their data with those outside the scientific community. To do so effectively requires new creative approaches, including prioritizing time spent on communications and improving incentives for scientists to publicize their research.

To increase the likelihood of translating scientific research into outcomes such as greater ecological restoration and management we also have to try and communicate with a hopeful mindset, otherwise we risk inaction through despair. There are restoration efforts in place, including the culling approach, planting kelp, and the re-introduction of sea stars which help keep the populations of purple sea urchins in check. That is to say, there are a number of tools which can be used to help restore and sustain kelp forests. To help make this happen though there needs to be more public support of action, which in turn means more activity in promoting public understanding of these tools (Pace et. al. 2010).

Public outreach can be encouraged in a variety of ways, including efforts to reward or incentivize effective science communication skills, evaluations of method efficacy, as well as advocating designated outreach time.

While outreach is effective in building public support for scientific work, scientists have found that there are barriers to carrying out such efforts: these range from concerns to maintaining a work-life balance, to perceived deficits in outreach and public communication skills. To help ensure broad swathes of the public are being reached there needs to be some level of reward for researchers on building their communication skills (Alamenciak & Murphy 2024).

Recent technological developments, and the rise of citizen science, show promise in both building public support for science through outreach, as well as leveraging public actions in carrying out further research. For example, NeMO-Net created a citizen science video game that was downloaded in over 73 countries and what NeMO-Net did for coral, and its 300 million+ users (Van Den Bergh et al., 2021), could it do the same for kelp forests?

Citizen science approaches can also be applied to engage the public in the process of kelp forest restoration itself. For example, successful restoration of kelp forests has been accomplished through removal of urchins along the Norwegian coast (Berge Remøe, 2024).

While kelp forests have experienced long-term declines over the past century (Saligumba, 2025), it also contains a number of divers motivated to replicate the success of the volunteer-led efforts found in Norway. These efforts have focused on culling purple sea urchins, which has been found to be a low-tech but successful method of restoring kelp forests through the reduction of overgrazing activity. Such efforts can be leveraged across the efforts of hundreds of scientific volunteer divers through organizations like Reef-check, which helps connect various community restoration efforts.

Another recent, and currently underutilized, approach to public engagement with science is the use of social media. For example, the video-sharing platform is algorithmically fine-tuned to engage millions of users daily based on inferred interests. Such a platform knows who would be interested in hearing about the latest scientific discoveries, and what aspects of current scientific research are of greatest interest to them.

Engaging the public more in the science behind these restoration efforts, as well as volunteer activities to help restore and sustain kelp forests is of increasing urgency.

As oceans warm and acidify due to sustained

fossil fuel use, and as urban runoff grows in scale, kelp forest ecosystems become increasingly vulnerable to new stressors. One such stressor has been the recent emergence of Sea Star Wasting Disease (SSWD). After more than a decade of investigation, scientists have recently identified the cause of SSWD as a bacterium known as *Vibrio P*. This disease has decimated sunflower sea star populations, with significant consequences for kelp forest ecosystems, as sunflower sea stars are among the predators keeping purple sea urchin populations in check (Prentice et al., 2025).

Unfortunately, a combination of environmental stressors has made sunflower sea stars particularly vulnerable to this bacterial infection, leading to the local extinction of all but two known reproductive females living in captivity in Southern California (McCrea & Makovec, 2025).

One of these females is currently housed at Heal the Bay, a marine research, outreach, and restoration organization that has been preparing this individual for spawning as part of its species recovery efforts. This could be great news for kelp forests since a sunflower sea star can consume up to ten urchins in a single day (Pena, 2025) presenting a possible solution for the removal of urchin barrens.

PHOTO : TAYLOR GRIFFITH

In carrying for this sea star, Heal The Bay has been actively engaging the public on their work, building support for their efforts.

If California can successfully reintroduce these sea stars, it could be a kinder, more ethical, and ultimately more ecocentric way to restore kelp forests than urchin culling.

Considering ethics is essential in restoration because you are making decisions that can have significant consequences for species and ecosystems. (Lee, 2025).

Continuing with the example of restoring sunflower sea star populations to restore kelp forests, there remains a good deal of nuance to communicate with the public and policy makers. These animals must be placed in an area where they will thrive, and will thrive in the coming years. For example, San Diego waters are getting so warm that kelp forests cannot thrive there, which may ultimately negate any attempts at restoring sunflower sea stars in those areas.

Guiding this decision-making process involves communicating and coordinating with various interests and professional groups, ranging from technical divers, marine biologists, economists, and policy makers. Understanding how to effectively carry this out may one day be supported with nascent technologies such as AI, but they are ultimately very human endeavors. The need to better understand this is increasingly urgent in the face of rapid environmental changes.

PHOTOS: KARLI KLEIN

The Sunflower Sea Star that is currently being housed at Heal the Bay Aquarium, through the American Zoological Association program (Adler, 2024), and is being prepared for spawning.

PHOTOS: KARLI KLEIN

EDITOR'S NOTE:

Ecological systems are very deeply connected to time and place, with relationships evolving across the landscape. How do we best understand the evolution of these systems? This essay investigates the role of visualizations and mapping in communicating the complexity of these systems, especially to the coastal communities being most affected by their degradation and restoration.

COMMUNICATION

Restoring California's kelp forests is not simply an ecological issue, but a social one. Restoration requires interdisciplinary approaches to reach audiences beyond the scientific community. While conversations surrounding restoration have started, they are widely inaccessible to the communities directly affiliated with California's kelp forests—such as indigenous nations, fisheries, and coastal communities whose everyday lives are tied to the ocean. Scientific research is too often communicated in an exclusionary way: Jargon-heavy academic language generates a culture and discourse that alienates those most impacted by climate change.

Rather than viewing science as a siloed discipline, we need to recognize that it relies on cultural, social, and economic components.

PHOTO : ALEC BATTISTONI

ART & VISUALS

Storytelling and art can communicate the urgent need for restoration in an accessible and constructive way; helping communities that are often left out of the conversation, and building emotional connections to help form a deeper understanding of kelp restoration. These communities need a comprehensive perspective to fully understand the complexity of the situation. It is not enough to simply say kelp canopy is declining, people need to know why it is declining and understand why that matters. By understanding keystone species in the ecosystem, like the sea otter and the sunflower sea star, people can start to narrate the dynamics of kelp forests and form a deeper understanding of these vital underwater ecosystems.

Visuals are a foundational part of understanding any discipline (Aisami, 2015). Picture books and sensory experience help form a rudimentary understanding of the world. Before a person reads, they visualize. When a mathematician needs to understand a function, they analyze the graph of that function.

Visuals are a fundamental part of forming a complex understanding of something. The word macroalgae on its own may seem abstract and hard to understand. However, with vivid imagery and descriptive language help becomes something familiar and recognizable: With long fronds that sway in the currents, kelp forests provide shelter and habitat for marine life, much like terrestrial forests do on land. Understanding the movement and characteristics of something helps a person understand that concept in a more intimate and personal way.

MAPPING

Geospatial mapping is an important tool to connect objects, natural spaces, and the environment that might otherwise be lost when relying solely on quantitative data. When you have a visual representation of your presence in a space, through geo-spatial mapping, it becomes personalized, and history is made visible in relation to yourself. While there are already powerful tools to track kelp canopy and estimate future loss or growth—like remote sensing or machine learning (Finger et al., 2021)—they often stop at the scientific level. With the progression of technology, society has the tools to make science

more accessible; instead of siloing disciplines and widening the gap between the scientific and social worlds, technology can contribute to a greater public knowledge. Communicating through art and geospatial storytelling can create true interdisciplinary restoration efforts along the California coastline.

Mapping is a powerful tool, however it is not enough to simply visual geographic data, we must also contextualize it. Counter Mapping is a critical approach to spatial analysis, prioritizing decolonial and indigenous-centered mapmaking (Boatcâ, 2021; Dalton & Stallmann 2018). It is strategic mapping, with the purpose of confronting unequal geographical structures (Boatcâ, 2021). It is vital to recognize spatial mapping as a practice lacking neutrality, and to acknowledge how it can hyperbolize data to reinforce confirmation bias. Counter Mapping can be used to visually represent native-land and new conservation areas for kelp forests that need protecting. This is a valuable tool in helping radically change the way kelp restoration efforts are practiced within California. By weaving together local and indigenous knowledge, storytelling, art, and geospatial analysis, restoration can become not only a scientific endeavor but something collaborative and community based.

PHOTO : ALEC BATTISTONI

5.6 Coastal Truths: Native People at the Frontlines of Shifting Shoreline Narratives

Words by Zee Zetino

EDITOR'S NOTE:

What of the indigenous nations who have stewarded the coasts of what we now call California? There are millenia of accumulated indigenous cultural knowledge about the coastal habitats within which kelp resides. What do we lose when we don't share these voices, what do we gain? The following essay focuses on these questions.

Native communities have sacred relationships with the coast and the open ocean, but they need land sovereignty, material support, and overall solidarity to rightfully restore and revitalize lands and waters.

AUTHOR'S DISCLAIMER: The following writing follows my personal style of writing and is in no way reflective of everyone's thoughts, political views, and opinions in the entirety of this report. My style of writing centers native people, while also recognizing my obligation as an Afro-indigenous person living on unceded Gabrielino-Tongva territory (Los Angeles), with the closest village to me known as Yaanga—the land of the poison oak. I'd also like to note the my reflections are in no way an attempt to speak or represent native tribes of California. In fact, I encourage individuals, organizations, and agencies at different levels of decision making to seek direct consultation, intentional collaboration, and provide significant material compensation for tribes descended from the lands where water (re)storation and re(vital)ization work is taking place. As a start, visit the Native Land Digital website. If you are doing kelp restoration work on or adjacent to Chumash territory, specifically the central coast, check out the

Chumash Sacred Sites page of the Chumash Heritage National Marine Sanctuary website within the heritage tab. I also encourage individuals to learn more about the Chumash, Salinan, or even the Kashia Band of Pomo Indians—coastal people with vibrant histories.

The purpose of my essay within this kelp assessment report is to highlight the critical need to properly represent native cultural history that exists along the coast of what is known as California, but which is distorted and/or absent in interpretive material overseen by organizational and governmental agencies. These centered efforts are in no manner my creations, nor are they my sole ideas, they are rather continuous efforts by indigenous communities. As an Afro-indigenous person from Kuscatan (El Salvador), I understand my responsibility within this scope of work and recognize my obligation to the people within communities and all fauna, flora, fungi, algae, bacteria, and everything in between. An obligation of utmost solidarity and continuous work towards true sovereignty over the land. Which is why, contributing my piece to this report, I recognize the importance of centering the cultural histories and interconnectedness native people have with sacred places like kelp forests. This means connect(ing) community members and visitors alike, to the history of the original stewards and protectors of the land and waters we reside on and near.

Kelp Forest

Kelp forests support nearly a thousand species of animals, from tiny snails to muscular sea lions.

In contrast to the seemingly barren cliffs above, there is a teeming forest beneath the surface of the cove. The kelp forests are an underwater gathering ground, attracting a crowd of creatures normally scattered throughout the surrounding waters.

From its surface fronds, the giant seaweed extends below, attached to rocks of the nearshore reef. This vertical ecosystem becomes a passageway between air, sea, and island worlds. Human divers can join pinnipeds, algae, fishes, and marine invertebrates in the green shadowed thickets.

IMAGE COURTESY OF NATIONAL PARK SERVICE (PUBLIC DOMAIN)

The land and water invites people to protect, recognize, respect, and honor native peoples, while also establishing an understanding of the displacement and disruption settler-colonialism had on Native communities; impacts which still exist today. Impacts which are exacerbating the climate crisis. While one doesn't need to be native or indigenous to recognize the need to include native history into all interpretive material, it's important that as people, we are uplifting the requests of native tribal communities to these lands and waters—sacred places.

Before skimming the water's surface, I'd like to share my personal experiences with interpretive material overseen by organizational and governmental agencies that I've encountered along parts of the California coast and overall outdoor spaces, and what prompted me to write this piece. I've had opportunities, both through work and ongoing love for the coast and ocean, to visit several coastal sites along California, many of which display inaccurate information about native people, use passive language regarding colonialism and capitalism, refer to native people in past tense, simply never mention native peoples, show present day images of Native people, let alone share their cultural connections

to the coast and open waters. An example of absent Chumash history and cultural connection to the kelp forest can be observed through the National Park Service (NPS) Anacapa Kelp Forest signage. When there is no native history presented in coastal areas like 'Anyapax, now known as Anacapa Island, there are significant impacts on both local communities and visitors. Significant impacts which are missed opportunities to invite local communities and visitors to protect, recognize, respect, and honor native people, land and water. In 2023, NPS released a report, sharing that 323,000 people visited the Channel Islands.

While the report didn't include exactly how many people visited 'Anyapax, I'd argue that even if one person visited and saw the kelp forest signage, it's one too many of a missed opportunity to educate a person on the rich stories of this site and the Chumash's cultural history, traditions, and relationships to kelp, abalone, and sea urchins alike. My personal experiences of observing and analyzing various interpretive signages along the coast informs me how interpretive material signage being displayed is missing the opportunity to educate mass local communities, ongoing visitors, and staff working for organizations and governmental agencies about native

peoples connection to the coast and marine ecosystems like the kelp forest. In addition, it also suggests the need for organizations and governmental agencies to improve their methods of outreach and engagement with native coastal communities in California when planning and implementing interpretive signages. My writing is not to shame, but instead a message of accountability and responsibility, and as a means to shift awareness as a catalyst for change within interpretive material as the first step towards land and water sovereignty.

In Nizhoni Tallas' research thesis paper, "It's a Sign: Understanding Variations In Telling Indigenous Histories Within Public Outdoor Spaces", she examined how Native people and their histories were being represented in interpretive signage at 14 sites within the Southwest region. Through her efforts, she concluded:

Overall, I found a large amount of variation from one site to another. No sites managed by US federal agencies showed a consistent presence of respect, representation, and relevance in their interpretive signs. In contrast, Navajo Tribal Park showed the most promise compared to other sites analyzed.

While Tallas examined interpretive signages specific to the southwest region, her work shines light on the need for organizations and governmental agencies to intentionally engage native communities, so that tribal communities are properly represented and people who visit these sites are accurately educated about tribal cultural histories (Tallas, 2024). In order to improve the interpretive signages overseen by national parks, monuments, and other public land managements, Tallas suggests the use of the Six R's of Indigenous Research: respect, relationship, representation, relevance, responsibility, and reciprocity (Tallas, 2024). Through her observations and documentations, she also noticed that the Navajo Tribe Park did a better job with their interpretive signage (Tallas, 2024). Reading examples like this one, reminds me how native and indigenous communities will continue to lead the way towards what we envision for our communities and how we envision it being done. I believe that if the Six R's of Indigenous Research are used across all levels of research and report-

ing, one day it will allow us to witness interpretive signage displaying and honoring living native community members like Alan Salazar all while showcasing his bull kelp rattles. Alan Salazar is a traditional storyteller, native educator, and a tribal elder in both the Fernandeano Tataviam and Ventureño Chumash tribes.

In order to improve the interpretive signages overseen by national parks, monuments, and other public land managements, Tallas suggests the use of the Six R's of Indigenous Research: RESPECT, RELATIONSHIP, REPRESENTATION, RELEVANCE, RESPONSIBILITY, AND RECIPROCITY (Tallas, 2024).

**Centering the
cultural histories and
interconnectedness
Native people have with
sacred places like kelp
forests..**

IMAGE : PUBLIC DOMAIN

**It invites
people to
protect,
recognize,
respect, and
honor Native
people, land
and water.**

ARTWORK : ZEE ZETINO

Blue Economy + Work Force

Authors : Chotcheyrith Ieng, Arianna Martinez

6.1 Introduction

The blue economy is, as defined by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), “a sustainable and equitable ocean and coastal economy that optimizes advances in science and technology to create value-added, data-driven economic opportunities and solutions to pressing societal needs” (NOAA, 2023). The blue economy has a wide range of impacts on both coastal and non-coastal communities. In the face of climate change, the need to preserve and sustainably use ocean resources and other waterway resources is more urgent than ever. Furthermore, “if American coastal counties were an individual country, they would rank third in the world in GDP, surpassed only by the United States and China. The prosperity and security of this nation is therefore predicated on the understanding, health, and sustainable use of our oceans, coasts, and Great Lakes” (NOAA, 2023).

It is also important to note that the Californian coast has been influenced by human activity for millennia, with the majority of this influence being under various forms of indigenous land management (Morris, J.A, et al., 2021). There is a key human element in the blue economy; which brings us to the questions of workforce development and sustainability. Sustainability is a key component to the preservation of ecological resources and is defined by social, economic, and environmental outcomes (Elkington, 2013; Alleway, et al., 2021)

In a growing Californian Blue Economy how does kelp fit in?

Aquaculture has been used by indigenous and coastal peoples from time immemorial. Synthesizing these practices, with modern techniques, leads to a set of practices known as restorative aquaculture. There is also a growing awareness for current aquaculture ventures to collaborate with indigenous peoples (Alleway, et al., 2021; Brown, 2024). Restorative aquaculture “occurs when commercial or subsistence aquaculture provides direct ecological benefits to the environment, with the potential to generate net positive environmental outcomes,” and can take many different forms (Alleway, et al., 2021). As the human population grows, a sustainable food source is another tool to reduce greenhouse gas emission (Alleway, et al., 2021). For the focus of our study we looked at giant kelp and bull kelp, whose forests provide great environmental, social, and economic value along the California coast. Kelp forests are an iconic part of California’s coastline and can create economic incentives through direct or indirect means.

Kelp forests have both intrinsic as well as extractive market value to people. This can also be defined as “market driven motivations” through direct extraction of kelp, the organisms that inhabit them for either direct consumption or processing into products, as well as more abstract valuations like carbon credits (Eger et al, 2021).

**In a growing
Californian
Blue
Economy
how does
kelp fit in?**

Intrinsic value is defined as “nonmarket motivations” like “...human cultural, recreational, and educational experiences within a kelp forest” (Eger et al, 2021).

Kelp forests often have a large influence in shaping local economies. Starting from providing jobs to the local communities to boosting the economy in the region as a whole.

The idea of kelp-based restorative aquaculture has sparked interest among researchers and business individuals. In California, one of the major barriers preventing the industry’s growth is the costly and lengthy process of granting permits.

Unfortunately, there is a concurrent and growing need for kelp forest restoration as there are a number of human-caused environmental stressors leading to the decline in forest coverage. For this study we explore the economic feasibility of kelp restoration projects along the coastline of California, while attempting to bridge the gap between current social issues like coastal access and workforce development.

We focus on the relationship between Californian kelp forests and the blue economy through the following lenses: Conservation, restoration & monitoring, aquaculture, and social sustainability.

PHOTO : TAYLOR GRIFFITH

We focus on the relationship between Californian kelp forests and the blue economy through the following lenses:

conservation, restoration & monitoring, aquaculture, and social sustainability.

ABALONE TANK AT THE CULTURED ABALONE FARM
PHOTO: ZEE ZETINO

6.2 Methods

To evaluate the role of the blue economy in kelp forest restoration and aquaculture we obtained information via a literature review, site visits at aquaculture facilities, as well as from interviewing people who work in aquaculture. Google scholar is the primary search engine that we used to obtain our resources, using the following key phrases in our searches: Economics of Californian Kelp Forests, Aquaculture and Kelp Forests, and Kelp Forest Restoration in California. Moreover, all of the papers were selected based on the most up to date finding and the relevant contents to our assessment. During site visits, we interviewed aquaculturists on their cultivation of kelp and associated species such as abalone. This method is preferred to understand the current issues and the opinion of people with hands-on experiences.

6.3 Findings

CONSERVATION

Conservation is the protection of natural resources while preservation is more closely related to protection of landscapes (National Parks Service, 2019). With the protection of landscapes the goal is more often the preservation of a part of the natural world due to its intrinsic value. With regards to the conservation of natural resources the goal is generally tied to something with a monetizable value. Recent research shows that “the average combined value per hectare per year of carbon storage, nutrient removal, and fisheries services ranged from \$38,799 (*Macrocystis*, South-eastern Pacific) to \$165,200 (*Laminaria*, North-western Atlantic)” (Eger et al, 2021). It is valuable to specify the plethora of kelp forest ecosystem services since it’s as an argument to further kelp forest restoration, which may in turn help preserve them on the basis of their intrinsic values.

California kelp forests are very productive systems that provide some key ecosystem services such as fisheries production, nutrient cycling, and carbon removal (Eger et al., 2023). Aside from the direct employment to manage MPAs, heritage sites, and research stations, these areas also have indirect economic benefits derived from being conservation sites such as enrichment of local fishers (Scorese J. & Kildow J., 2014).

PHOTO : SAMANTHA AGUILAR

Heritage sites have been found to have economic impact, however the extent of these impacts are difficult to observe (Scorese J. & Kildow J., 2014).

Protections like “Sanctuary Designation can impact local economies” in the following direct and indirect ways (Scorese J. & Kildow J., 2014):

1. **Government expenditures**
2. **Money raised by local NGOs**
3. **Increased coastal tourism and the increases in relevant business revenues.**
4. **Increased property values, property taxes, and business, local, state and federal tax revenues**

While there are general benefits to preserving kelp forests, each coastal community, its local ecology, and its economy have unique aspects (Scorese J. & Kildow J., 2014). The preservation of kelp forests are also often driven by local actions, rather than any top-down directed activities. With these local actions, “many kelp forest restoration projects are supported by volunteer divers, non profits and other NGOs also rely on individuals who donate their time, this has actually been found to have a positive economic impact on the local area” this is also the case in kelp forest restoration in California (Scorese J. & Kildow J., 2014; Eger, et al., 2022). Fortunately, along the Californian coast, there are specific success stories of thriving blue economies, like Monterey Bay (Scorese J. & Kildow J., 2014)

Conservation is the protection of natural resources, while preservation is more closely related to the protection of landscapes

(National Parks Service, 2019).

PHOTO : TAYLOR GRIFFITH

Figure 18: Total Economic Value (TEV) Framework

RESTORATION & MONITORING

There are two main categories of funding for kelp restoration projects: Government and private funding. Governments generally fund a restoration project based on ecosystem services that the project provides. Private funders expect cash benefits in return before they decide to fund, unless they declare themselves as non-profit organizations. In order to increase support for restoration, we need a quantitative value of kelp forest ecosystems that can be integrated into government decisions (Eger et al., 2020).

According to the Total Economic Value (TEV) Framework (Fig. 18), restoration values can be classified into use and non-use values. For use values, it can be divided further into direct and indirect use values. Direct use values tend to be more easily measured than its indirect counterparts. For kelp forest restorations, direct extractive values come directly from kelp products, whilst the direct non-extractive ones are those of the education and ecotourism sectors.

AQUACULTURE

Aquaculture plays a key role in both research and conservation of aquatic species and is defined as “the farming of aquatic organisms, including bait-fish, crustaceans, food fish, mollusks, ornamental fish, sport or game fish, and other aquaculture products. Farming involves some form of intervention in the rearing process, such as seeding, stocking, feeding, protection from predators, etc” (USDA, 2023). Research of seaweed is furthered by aquaculture and vice versa. Exciting new technological and research aquaculture developments may be able fulfill the blue economy’s sustainability needs (Charrier et al., 2017; Talley et al., 2025). Aquaculture is also an impactful tool in conservation and restoration, and can be used to protect and care for endangered species like the Sunflower Sea Star (Laura Rink, pers. comm.). Aquaculture has also been conducted by various indigenous and tribal groups for thousands of years (Morris, J.A, et al., 2021). In fact, “aquaculture has been practiced sustainably for millenia by many local and indigenous communities for food, trade, cultural, and environmental outcomes, with many of these systems an important precursor and parallel to this restorative aquaculture approach.

Importantly, when discussing the need to ‘re-store’ our natural systems or lamenting the loss of essential marine habitats, conservationists are most often referring to pre-colonial levels of environmental connectivity and abundance, which were often the result of local and Indigenous resource management” (Alleway et al., 2021). Sustainably expanding the blue economy is an exciting opportunity for the California coast. According to the USDA "2023 Census of Aquaculture," California has a total of 79 aquaculture farms, 47 are Food Fish Farms, 4 are algae farms, and 3 miscellaneous farms for microalgae and sea vegetables (USDA, 2023).

Globally, 23.8 million tonnes of seaweed are produced every year with an estimated value of 6.4 billion USD (Moffitt, 2014). Due to the lengthy and complex permitting process for aquaculture in the state, California is struggling to keep up with other coastal and island states, such as Maine, Alaska, and Hawaii. During the course of this project, we were able to visit and study a few examples of onshore and offshore aquaculture in southern California: Ocean Rainforest and The Cultured Abalone Farm. Ocean rainforest is an offshore seaweed aquaculture farm in Santa Barbara. They receive funding from many private donors and organizations, such as the

Grantham Foundation for the Protection of the Environment, Katapult Ocean's Deep Blue fund, and the Builders Vision (Ocean Rainforest, 2024). They are currently in the process of research and development; transforming their farm from a research purpose farm to a commercial farm that yields a profit and can sustainably support their aquaculture project in the long run without being entirely dependent on external funding.

The Cultured Abalone Farm is an example of onshore aquaculture and was originally focused solely on abalone aquaculture, but has started to develop co-cultural techniques with red seaweeds (“Home | the Cultured Abalone Farm” 2023). In addition, the abalone farm is harvesting the purple sea urchins from the ocean to feed them more in their farm, hoping that those urchin’ gonads will reach the size of the red sea urchins which is more favorable for business purposes. According to the manager of the Cultured Abalone Farm, “it is tricky to say whether purple sea urchins that were harvested from the sea and being fed on land will have the same market as the red sea urchins.” These efforts contribute to less sea urchins in the area, which is exceptionally advantageous for kelp habitats and all the parties involved.

California has a total of 79 aquaculture farms, 47 are Food Fish Farms, 4 are algae farms, and 3 miscellaneous farms (microalgae & sea vegetables, USDA 2023 Census of Aquaculture)

PHOTO: ZEE ZETINO

Seaweeds, like giant kelp and bull kelp, are known as extractive species and potential species candidates for restorative aquaculture (Alleway et al., 2021). Restorative Aquaculture can take many different forms, however it "occurs when commercial or subsistence aquaculture provides direct ecological benefits to the environment, with the potential to generate net positive environmental outcomes" (Alleway, et al., 2021).

As a model of restorative aquaculture, Integrated Multi-trophic Aquaculture (IMTA), can potentially boost the economic stability of an individual aquaculture business and reduce its environmental footprint (Alleway, et al., 2021; Hossen et al., 2022). Urchin ranching is the process of removing urchins from the environment to provide a "high-value seafood while offering the opportunity to restore healthy kelp forests" (Hentschel, et al., 2025). Urchin ranching has been successful in other countries such as Norway, Japan, and Canada (Hentschel, et al., 2025).

In a recent study surveying 9 seaweed farms in California, Oregon, and Washington State farmers were asked "from your perspective, what can be done in order to expand seaweed farming within the United States?" (Donovan, 2025). In response to this survey 28% of farms expressed that "their top industry concerns... social licenses with local communities, diversifying market opportunities, expanding the number of federal and state Aquaculture Opportunity areas, (AOAs), developing worker training programs, and funding the construction of seaweed processing facilities" followed by "24% of farms recommended increasing market demands for domestic seaweed products, 17% of farms recommended increasing the number of federal and state Aquaculture Opportunity Areas (AOA's) throughout the U.S." (Donovan, 2025). Surprisingly, only "14% of farms recommended simplifying the U.S. regulatory apparatus" (Donovan, 2025). However, when asked, "what have been some of your greatest challenges operating your farm?...The top three challenges for study participants in 2023 were permitting and navigating regulations at 34%, the other thoughts category at 21%, and weather-related complications at 14%". Other thoughts included the following topics: "Not In My Backyard (NIMBY)

phenomenon, a lack of industry investors and stakeholders, Anthropogenic Climate Change, market barriers, limited processing infrastructure for farmed seaweed products, payroll difficulties, labor shortages, and the predatory nature of the seaweed genus *Ulva*" (Donovan, 2025).

SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY

For the blue economy to continue to grow sustainably so must the workforce and other economic deliverables, like training programs and their funding sources. In California, an increased interest in the blue economy has resulted in Blue Economy and Climate Action Pathways (BECAP) an initiative that "...spearheads efforts to address the evolving employment landscape in Los Angeles' ocean-related markets, aligning seamlessly with California's climate action and environmental justice priorities" (Los Angeles Regional Consortium, 2024).

PHOTO : TAYLOR GRIFFITH

This initiative is vital for the continued growth of the blue economy in Los Angeles and for full transparency also funded this report (Los Angeles Regional Consortium, 2024).

This increased interest speaks to the value of technical skills, certification, and education for this sector. A science and community-based approach to identifying these areas, designated as AOAs, helps minimize interference with other enterprises, account for current fishing patterns, and protect the ecosystem” (NOAA, 2025). Excitingly, “modeling results identified eight AOA options in the North study area off Santa Barbara, California, and two AOA options in the Central North study area off Santa Monica, California” amounting to a total of 10 Californian AOAs (Morris, J.A, et al., 2021).

There are NGOs spearheading the charge like Greenwave, whose “goal is to support 10,000 farmers, catalyzing the scaled planting of regenerative ocean crops to yield meaningful eco-

nomics and climate impacts... [and] focus on two program areas: Training and Innovation” (Green-Wave, 2025).

Traditional ecological knowledge can also be integrated with these aquaculture training programs. Some examples of such programs are the Tolowa Dee-ni' Nation Kelp Guardians, Kashia Band of Pomo Indians, Kashia Department of Environmental Planning, Ocean Origins, and the Clam Garden Network (Laucci, et al., 2025; Ablan & Jimenez, 2021; Kashia Pomo Indian Tribe, 2025; Ocean Origins, 2025; Clam Garden Network, 2025). This work is important because “traditional knowledge provides a historical baseline that, when integrated with contemporary scientific approaches, serves as a holistic framework to understand the consequences of climate variability and climate change for coastal ecosystems” (McCoy, et al. 2017). Overall, social sustainability is crucial to the future success of Californian Kelp forests.

PHOTO : SAMANTHA AGUILAR

6.4 Conclusions and recommendations

Our recommendations are the following: sustainable use of the California coastline must include social collaboration with local communities and tribal & indigenous peoples, more streamlined policy, and continued funding of blue economy sector training and education programs.

California has the opportunity to improve the regulatory process and increase sustainability within the blue economy. There is strong scientific evidence that a more integrated approach in aquaculture, like IMTA models, can improve water quality, provide habitat, and help mitigate greenhouse gas emissions (Alleway et al., 2021). Restorative aquaculture has the potential to integrate coastal access, food security, and mitigate greenhouse gas emissions all while reconnecting people to land and waterways (Alleway et al., 2021; Brown, 2024).

California can follow other state's models, like Washington, on how to better integrate indigenous and tribal leadership (Brown, 2024). As for general seaweed production in the U.S., current levels are relatively low by international standards, however solutions like IMTA or increased seaweed processing plants are potential solutions, although more research is needed (Donovan, 2025).

A focus on native species in offshore aquaculture within an IMTA model is key to restorative aquaculture (Alleway et al., 2021). This brings us to the training, cultivating multiple species takes multiple skill sets. California needs to continue committing to workforce training and development for all aspects of the blue economy for it to be successful.

Within the next five years, California should prioritize expanded community outreach to build a network of Indigenous and Native leaders across the state in collaboration with local Indigenous and tribal communities. The Clam Garden Network, an Indigenous-led initiative focused on revitalizing traditional clam garden practices, intertribal collaboration, and coastal ecosystem stewardship, presents a strong model and potential partner for such efforts. (Clam Garden Network, 2025). With respect and permission from Tribal and Indigenous groups, traditional practices should be incorporated as well as Tribal leadership in both policy and workforce development. Worker training programs that incorporate tribal community outreach can be used as the model for expanding the social equity in the blue economy. The overall permitting process for aquaculture needs to be more streamlined and an increased number of AOAs sensitive to social impacts, would help allow for more aquaculture opportunities.

PHOTO : TAYLOR GRIFFITH

A note about the language of crisis :

“Humans continually generate new words, and in turn those words shape us, binding our inner lives to the stories we tell about ourselves and the world” (Center for Humans and Nature, n.d.)

As the climate crisis unfolds, our vocabularies must expand to capture the full range of our experiences. Encounters with the natural world elicit emotions—from elation to devastation—and words help us express both the depth of our ties to particular landscapes and the grief of losing them.

An expanded eco-emotional vocabulary allows us to name the joy, grief, wonder, and unease that come from deep connection with the earth. Language does more than describe; it fosters responsibility and care for the places and beings with which we are entangled. Words reveal animacy, highlight interconnection, and situate us within living systems. They also shape action: the words we choose can either distance us from the world or draw us closer to it. Yet many dominant languages have framed nature as something outside of us—an object or commodity—reinforcing separation rather than connection. New words can help us see the world not as a resource, but as a web of relationships in which we are fully involved.

For centuries, science has tried to purge itself of feeling, cutting off its roots in natural philosophy, where wonder, reflection, and metaphysics were central to understanding the world. Bringing emotion and imagination back into science means embracing vocabularies broad enough to hold resilience, grief, wonder, and responsibility. Inspiration can be found in older linguistic traditions, in Indigenous languages, and in non-English words that carry animacy and relationality, emphasizing human and nonhuman interconnection.

Developing such vocabularies makes visible the losses we face, reminds us that the world we love is under threat, and can inspire collective action to protect it. By leaning into a broader emotional vocabulary, we create space for a more honest conversation about the lived dimensions of the environmental crisis. This diversity of expression deepens our connection to the earth and strengthens our ability to respond with care and urgency.

Developing an Eco-Emotional Vocabulary

Below are nine emotional experiences that people may encounter through their relationship with the natural world. Each term offers a nuanced perspective, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of our deep connection to the environment. **SOURCE :** (<https://auragoldman.co.uk/developing-eco-emotion-vocabulary/>)

1. **Euterria:** A Profound Oneness with Nature
2. **Eco-grief:** Navigating Loss and Disconnection
3. **Solastalgia and Hiraeth:** Homesickness and Longing
4. **Terrafurie:** Unleashing Anger for Environmental Change
5. **Topophilia and Cynefin:** Emotional Bonds and Belonging
6. **Eco-guilt and Flygskam:** Navigating Shame and Overwhelm
7. **Soliphilia:** Political Affiliation and Personal Responsibility
8. **Eco-paralysis:** Confronting Powerlessness and Apathy
9. **Tierratrauma:** Grieving Sudden Environmental Change

Check out these resources on reimagining and expanding the language we use for nature:

[Sumaúma Journal:](#) writings that expose the destruction and injustices happening in the Amazon by using language that centers non-human perspectives and experiences.

[More-than-Humans Project:](#) a multimedia work that personifies an Amazonian tree to reveal its intricate ecological relationships and our kinship with other-than-human life.

[The Bureau of Linguistical Reality:](#) Artists Heidi Quante and Alicia Escott, work to create new words for emotions, experiences, and phenomena related to the climate crisis and our connections with the living world.

Questions to ask when (re)considering scientific terminology in EEB (Ecology and Evolutionary Biology)

We recommend that individuals critically assess the disciplinary terminology of their subfield. Below are some guiding questions:•

History. What is the etymology/origin of a term? Does its origin celebrate dominant narratives or oppressive norms? Does it commemorate violence or perpetuate prejudicial stereotypes?

Context. How might members of marginalized communities have different or negative experiences with a term, irrespective of the intentions of those using the term? How can EEB learn from, and center, those experiences in conversations about disciplinary terminology?

Community. Who has participated in conversations about the impact of a term, or about recommendations for more inclusive alternative terminology? Do such conversations center those most marginalized by that term?

Interdisciplinarity. How has a term been discussed in the critical humanities and social sciences? What new insights about terminology (and its histories, meanings, and impacts) do science and technology studies, the environmental humanities, or the rhetoric of science add to EEB?

Implementation. If a term has harmful associations, what alternative term(s) might more inclusively convey the same scientific concept? How can more inclusive alternatives be integrated into research, teaching, and mentoring?

(From championing inclusive terminology in ecology and evolution. Trends in ecology & evolution, may 2023, by cheng et al, scientific life)

Biology

Autonomous Robot: A robot that can perform tasks by itself without supervision.

Bioaccumulate: The gradual gathering and increasing of substance(s) within a living organism.

Biomass: The total quantity or weight of a specific organism in a given area or volume.

Bioremediation: The process of using living organisms to absorb, store, and clean up pollutants from soil, water, and/or air.

Biodiversity: The variety of life within a specific habitat.

Cadmium: 48th element from the periodic table with symbol (Cd); a toxic heavy metal pollutant released by industrial or agricultural runoff.

Carbon dioxide: (CO₂) Naturally occurring greenhouse gas which contributes to warming the climate; the largest source of carbon dioxide emissions comes from the burning of fossil fuels.

Carbon sequestration: The process of removing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and storing it in a stable form such as plants, algae, soils, or the ocean.

Copper: 29th element of the periodic table with symbol (Cu); a metal pollutant primarily introduced into the environment from mining, industrial processes, agricultural processes, or runoff.

Culling: The removal of certain organisms from an environment to reduce their numbers.

Degradation: The process of breaking down matter.

Embryonic: Relating to an embryo; referring to the multicellular diploid organism that develops from a fertilized egg and grows into the mature complex seaweed.

Gametophytes: A multicellular, haploid (single set of chromosomes) phase in the life cycle that produces gametes (sex cells) for sexual reproduction.

Intertidal: The area of the seashore which is covered at high tide and revealed at low tide.

Keystone species: An organism that has a strong impact on its environment relative to its abundance, affecting the whole ecosystem's structure and function.

Kilometers: Metric unit represented as km, 1 km = 1000 meters (about 0.62 miles).

Macroalgae: Large algae (seaweed) which is a broad group of eukaryotic photosynthetic marine organisms; unlike microalgae, they possess plant-like structural features and grow to large sizes.

Macroscopic: Visible to the naked eye.

Microalgae: Single-celled, photosynthetic microorganisms that primarily live in aquatic environments.

Microbiome: A community of microorganisms that include bacteria, viruses, fungi, protozoa that live on a specific site.

Microscopic: So small as to only be visible with a microscope.

Morphology: The physical characteristics of kelp including both their external appearance and internal organization.

Nitrogen: The 7th element of the periodic table with symbol (N); nonmetal that is considered one of the core elements of life along with carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, phosphorus, sulfur; excess nitrogen can act as a pollutant and can be released from burning of fossil fuels, agriculture, and wastewater.

Non-calcifying: Refers to organisms that do not need calcium deposits for their physiology; calcifying organisms use calcium carbonate to build their shells or skeletons.

Nurseries: Habitats where young organisms are born and raised.

Organic carbon: Carbon (element 14) found in organic compounds typically derived from living organisms; can come in the forms soil organic carbon, dissolved organic carbon, particulate organic carbon.

PAHs: (Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons) A group of chemicals that form from the burning of organic substances like coal, oil or wood; have been found to be carcinogenic towards humans, fish, and other animals.

Phosphates: An ionic functional group (PO₄)³⁻ that is a vital nutrient for life and essential for DNA and cellular energy; however, they are a common pollutant resulting from runoff, human and animal waste, industrial activities, and agriculture.

Phosphorus: Element 15 from the periodic table; acts as a critical nutrient required for all biological organisms; the common form of phosphorus used in these organisms comes as phosphate.

Photosynthesis: The process by which plants, algae, or some bacteria use sunlight, water, and carbon dioxide to create their own food in the form of glucose.

Prebiotic: A prebiotic is a substance that nourishes beneficial microorganisms in their surrounding environment, promoting improved growth and health.

Probiotic: Live microorganisms that, when consumed in adequate amounts, provide health benefits to the host.

Quicklime: A white, fine powder made of calcium oxide, used to exterminate sea urchins.

Sargassum horneri: An invasive brown algae native to Japan and Korea that can outcompete native species of kelp given the right conditions.

Sea star wasting syndrome: A disease fatal to the California sea star. This disease causes tissue loss which then progresses into disintegration and death.

Seedbanks: A facility that stores and preserves seeds (for kelp this is gametophytes) from various species for the long term to protect genetic diversity and serve as a resource in the future.

Sporophyte: One of the two alternating multicellular phases in the life cycles of plants and algae.

Sustainability: The ability to create and maintain healthy, equitable, and diverse communities and ecosystems.

Teragrams: A unit of mass from the metric system, one trillion grams (10^{12}).

Thermal tolerance: An organism's ability to physiologically adjust and withstand exposure to high temperatures and heat stress.

Transplantation: A direct form of kelp restoration which uses juvenile or adult kelp from a wild population, laboratory-cultured kelp, or beach-cast individuals and introduces them into the desired area through a suite of creative techniques (e.g., ropes, gravel).

Trophic redundancy: The presence of multiple species that have the same role within the food web.

Weedy turf algae: Fast-growing, filamentous carpets of algae that uptake substantial amounts of nutrients and can grow quickly in low nutrient conditions.

Zinc: (Zn) A metallic element with atomic number 30; a vital micronutrient for plankton and other marine animals. In high concentration resulting from industrial waste and urban runoff, it becomes a pollutant.

Modeling

Aquaculture Opportunity Areas (AOA): Geographic area that has been evaluated to determine its potential suitability for commercial aquaculture by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration.

Average Diffuse Attenuation Coefficient: A measure of how quickly light gets absorbed in the water column at a specific wavelength.

Bathymetry depth: The measurement of water depth in oceans, seas, lakes, and rivers.

Bathymetry layer: A raster file representing the depth of the seafloor at a global scale.

Chlorophyll concentration: The amount of chlorophyll-a present in phytoplankton and other aquatic plants in water.

Dissolved iron concentration: The amount of iron that is dissolved and suspended in seawater, as opposed to particulate iron.

Dissolved molecular oxygen: The amount of oxygen molecules freely present and dispersed within a liquid.

Marine protected areas (MPAs): Safeguarded ocean regions designated by governments or international organizations to conserve natural resources, protect habitats, and support biodiversity.

Mixed layer depth: The deepest layer affected by turbulent mixing, which marks the width of the upper ocean that interacts with the atmosphere.

Nitrate concentration: The amount of nitrate (NO_3^-) present in a specific volume of seawater.

pH: The logarithmically scaled concentration of H^+ ions found in water. This scale typically runs from highly acidic (0) to highly alkaline (14).

Phosphate concentration: The amount of phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) present in a specific volume of seawater.

Photosynthetically available radiation: The amount of light present at a specific range of wavelengths that plants and other photosynthetic organisms use to drive the process of photosynthesis.

Phytoplankton concentration: The density of microscopic marine algae, also known as phytoplankton, found in a given volume of seawater.

Random forest model: A machine learning model that predicts outcomes by utilizing multiple decision trees.

Shared socioeconomic pathways: A set of various climate change scenarios of projected socioeconomic global changes up to 2100, used to describe differing model climates.

Sixth phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CIMP6): Latest phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project initiative focused on advancing climate modeling to improve understanding of the Earth's climate system and future projections.

Salinity: The total amount of salt dissolved in a body of seawater.

Silicate concentration: The amount of silicate ions (SiO_4^{4-}) present in seawater.

Species distribution models: A model which predicts the occurrence or abundance of a species across geographic space and time using environmental data.

True skill statistic (TSS): A measure of model accuracy; it is calculated as the true positive rate (sensitivity) plus true negative rate (specificity) minus 1.

Topographic aspect: The direction that a seabed slope faces.

Topographic slope: The steepness of seabed, calculated as the ratio of vertical elevation change (y factor) to horizontal distance (x factor).

Terrain ruggedness index: The depth changes between adjacent points of the seabed.

Topographical position index: A comparison of the depth of seabed points to the mean elevation of adjacent points.

Total cloud fraction: The fractional area of a given space that is covered by clouds.

Policy & Governance

Aquaculture: The farming of aquatic plants and animals, including kelp, for commercial, restoration, or subsistence purposes.

Aquaculture Lease or Permit: A legal authorization granting rights to cultivate kelp or other seaweeds in designated areas. Issued by agencies such as the California State Lands Commission, California Coastal Commission, and NOAA for federal waters.

California Coastal Act (1976): State law requiring permits for coastal development, restoration, and aquaculture to ensure protection of coastal and marine resources.

California Coastal Commission (CCC): The state agency responsible for regulating coastal development and protecting coastal resources under the California Coastal Act.

California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW): Agency overseeing fisheries, wildlife, and habitat conservation; issues scientific collecting and restoration permits.

California Environmental Quality Act (CEQA): A state law mandating environmental review of proposed projects to minimize ecological impacts before approval.

Clean Water Act (Sections 401 & 404): Federal law regulating water pollution and discharges into U.S. waters. Section 401 provides state-level certification; Section 404 governs discharge of dredged or fill material, overseen by the Army Corps of Engineers.

Ecosystem-based management (EBM): A holistic approach to managing natural resources that considers ecological relationships, cumulative impacts, and sustainability.

Endangered Species Act (ESA) Consultation: A regulatory process ensuring restoration or aquaculture projects do not harm endangered species or their critical habitats.

Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM): A governance approach that coordinates policies across agencies and stakeholders to manage coastal resources sustainably.

Marine Life Protection Act (MLPA): California law establishing a statewide network of MPAs to conserve biodiversity and ecosystems.

National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA): Federal law requiring environmental assessments or impact statements for major projects involving federal agencies.

National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA): Federal agency conducting ocean and climate research, overseeing fisheries management, and issuing aquaculture approvals in federal waters.

Ocean Protection Council (OPC): California state body advancing ocean and coastal policy through science-based management, partnerships, and funding.

Permitting Hub: A proposed centralized system to streamline, coordinate, and make transparent the permitting process for marine restoration.

Private Lands Aquaculture Permit: Authorization required to farm kelp or other aquatic species on privately owned submerged lands.

Restoration Permit: Legal approval allowing habitat enhancement or ecological restoration, often requiring multi-agency coordination.

Scientific Collecting Permit (SCP): Permit authorizing the collection of marine organisms for research purposes, regulated by CDFW.

State Lands Commission (SLC): California agency managing sovereign lands, including submerged coastal lands, and issuing leases for aquaculture.

Water Quality Certification (Section 401): Approval from the State Water Resources Control Board confirming that projects meet water quality standards under the Clean Water Act.

Science Communication

Affective ecologies: In the context of environmental studies and ecocriticism, refers to the study of how emotions and feelings, both human and non-human, shape our relationship with the natural world.

Allokelping: The act of mutual exfoliation (to remove dead skin) between two whales.

Animacy: Refers to a grammatical and semantic feature found in some languages that distinguishes between living and non-living entities. It's a way of categorizing nouns based on their perceived "liveness" or sentience.

Animacy Theory: Encourages recognizing more-than-human lives (plants, animals, fungi, ecosystems) as active agents, not just passive resources.

Apocalyptic Ecology: The beholding of ecological relationships in times of rapid change, where hybridization and even mutation can sometimes emerge as (eco)systemic survival strategies.

Baseline Bias: When a project's target for a healthy ecosystem is based on an arbitrary or incomplete idea of the past, rather than the full ecological history.

Benefits for Humans: Cultural ecosystem services or sometimes called psychological ecosystem services.

Biosemiotics: The capacity of living organisms to navigate their environments through the processing of signs.

Bioclimatology: The interdisciplinary study of the relationships between climate and living organisms. It examines how climate influences the distribution, characteristics, and activities of plants, animals, and humans, and how these organisms, in turn, impact the climate.

Biophilia Hypothesis: A theory that humans have an innate, genetically based affinity towards other life forms and natural systems.

Capitolocene: Proposed alternative term for the Anthropocene, emphasizing that the current environmental crisis is driven by the logic of capitalism and the exploitation of both human labor and natural resources.

Casa Perdida: Spanish and Portuguese term to describe the fear of losing one's home to climate events.

Cognitive and emotional dimensions of knowledge: Interconnecting sciences and arts allows space for cognitive as well as emotional dimensions of knowledge.

Co-Governance of Research: Tribal and local communities help determine research questions, methods, and interpretation.

Deep Ecology: Goes beyond symptoms to address the root causes of ecological destruction. It challenges anthropocentrism (human-centered thinking) and argues that all living beings have intrinsic value, regardless of their usefulness to humans. It calls for deep cultural, political, and ethical transformation—rethinking how humans see themselves in relation to the Earth.

Ecocide: The destruction of ecosystems through colonialism, capitalism, and their subprocesses. Contributing to a lack of access to land-based living and the displacement of different marginalized identities.

Ecolinguistics: A field of study that explores the role of language in the life-sustaining interactions of humans, other species, and the physical environment.

Epistemic Humility: Recognizing that Western science has limits and benefits from relational intelligence.

Extinction of Experience: Decline in positive, direct human–nature interactions due to the loss of natural spaces and a reduced desire to engage with them.

Extirpation (of a species): The state or condition of having become locally or regionally extinct.

Futuralgia: Grief for possible futures.

Homeorhesis: The tendency of a dynamic system, particularly a biological one, to return to a specific trajectory or path of change after being disrupted.

Holobionts: An assemblage of a host and the many other species living in or around it, which together form a discrete ecological unit through symbiosis.

Koyaanisqatsi: Life out of balance.

Kelp Paddy: A floating mass of kelp, similar to a raft.

Mermerosity: Being worried about the possible passing of the familiar and its replacement by that which does not sit comfortably within one's sense of place.

Napëpë: Yanomami language, for colonizer/white, can be translated as enemy or outsider.

Nature Apathy: Younger generations in urbanized regions are losing emotional affinity to nature (videophilia hypothesis).

Nature Relatedness: A psychological construct that describes how close an individual's relationship is with nature.

Personalized Ecology: The study of the direct interactions between individual people and nature, including their ecological dimensions.

Pristine Reference State (PRS): Represents an ideal condition set as a target for restored ecosystems; considered to be in an original or un-altered state and typically characterized by high levels of biodiversity, functional processes, and spatiotemporal heterogeneity.

Regime Shift: Large, abrupt, persistent changes in the structure and function of ecosystems, the climate, financial systems, or other complex systems. The shift between kelp-dominated habitat to urchin-dominated habitat may constitute a regime shift if it persists.

Relational Ontology: Where humans are embedded in, rather than separate from, ecological systems.

Revenge of the Earth: Climate change in the Yanomani language.

Robust Novel Ecosystems (RNE): Novel ecosystems that demonstrate a capacity to withstand and adapt to disturbances while maintaining their structure and function.

Shallow Ecology: Focuses on short-term, surface-level solutions to environmental problems—like pollution control, resource efficiency, or technological fixes. Its primary concern is often human well-being and preventing harm to people in wealthy societies, rather than questioning deeper causes of ecological crisis.

Shifting Baseline: When measurements of a system/habitat/population are established as a baseline by comparison against previous reference points, often without knowledge that those previous points represent significant changes from an even earlier state of the system.

Shifting Baseline Syndrome: A gradual change in our accepted norms and expectations for the environment across generations, resulting in a diminishing motivation to support pro-nature policies and management actions.

Solastalgia: The homesickness or grief for a degraded home and a distressingly changing environment.

Symbiocene: A proposed future in which the interaction of humans with other living beings is symbiotic. Emphasizing a balanced coexistence and mutual companionship between humans and nature.

Terrafurie: Anger targeted at those who command the forces of Earth destruction; protective anger.

Three Modes of Interaction: Physical presence (e.g., forest walks, gardening), indirect exposure (e.g., seeing nature through windows), vicarious/mediated experiences (e.g., documentaries, social media).

Trans-Corporeality: A theory of interconnectedness of human and non-human bodies through material exchanges.

Blue Economy & Workforce

Ecosystem Services: Products and services of a healthy ecosystem that humans benefit from and may have associated monetary value.

Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture: A method of aquaculture with two or more species from different trophic levels.

Offshore Aquaculture: Aquaculture occurring in the open ocean.

Onshore Aquaculture: Aquaculture occurring on land and in tanks, ponds, etc.

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This internship program has supported a number of students, from a diverse array of backgrounds and community colleges in the Los Angeles area, to better understand the benefits and difficulties associated with kelp forest restoration in California. The result of this work is a report which covers the biology of giant kelp and bull kelp, the two dominant canopy-forming kelp of California, as well as models predicting suitable habitat areas under current and future conditions, environmental policy, the role of art and communication in science, as well as opportunities for the further development of the blue economy.